

Open Book Collective: Stakeholder and Sustainability Evaluation

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About the Open Book Collective

Open Book Collective is a UK-based registered charity that delivers sustainable new funding streams to book publishers and open publishing service providers, all deeply committed to open access. University libraries can use the Open Book Collective to subscribe to Supporter Programmes offered by our members. In return, supporters receive direct benefits, public recognition, as well as helping collectively fund a fairer future for open access books. We help publishers move away from having to rely on Book Processing Charges to fund open access books. We see these kinds of charges as unfair, preventing many authors from accessing the benefits of open access. They are also financially unsustainable, placing an ever increasing economic strain on university budgets.

About this report

The report is an output of the Copim Open Book Futures project (2023–2026). The project builds upon the pioneering work of the COPIM project (2019–2023), and is led by Lancaster University. Open Book Futures aims to initiate a step-change in the ambition, scope and impact of community-led open access book publishing. The stakeholder research that this report draws on was led by Judith Fathallah, with stakeholder interviews conducted by Francesca Corazza, Joe Deville, Judith Fathallah and Izabella Penier. Deville, Fathallah and Penier are all based at Lancaster University and are either fully or partially seconded to the Open Book Collective as part of the Open Book Futures project. Corazza works for the Open Book Collective.

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This report is an output of the Copim Open Book Futures project, co-funded by Arcadia and the Research England Development Fund. The project is led by Lancaster University, with Open Book Collective as one of the project partners.

Foreword by the Managing Director

As this report explores in detail, the Open Book Collective (OBC) is dedicated to helping deliver a fairer, sustainable future for open access book publishing. As an organisation, our history so far, over the course of just under four years, has been marked by a sequence of milestones. One was our legal incorporation in May 2022, just under 12 months before the end of the three and a half year Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs (COPIM) project.¹ There was also the launch of the OBC's digital platform, in December 2022, followed by the OBC receiving its first subscription, from the University of Manchester, in February 2023. Yet another key moment was the formal registration of the OBC as a charity, by the Charity Commission of England and Wales, in December 2023. This occurred during the life of COPIM's follow-on project: the three-year Copim Open Book Futures (OBF) project, which has now concluded.²

This report marks arguably the most significant milestone to date: the OBC's move from being a near wholly grant funded organisation to full financial independence. From the 1st May 2026 onwards, the OBC will be reliant on a combination of the reserves it has accrued and future income from its Members Library Supporter Programmes, with all other external income streams having ceased, at least for now.

This is a moment that the OBC team has been planning for, for some time, and towards the end of this report, we will reflect on OBC's financial progress to date and what its plans are for the coming months and years. However, it is also an opportunity for the OBC to take stock of its place within the wider landscape. So, alongside considering the numerical nuts and bolts of OBC's past and future work, the report also gathers together views from the communities that we have been engaging with over the course of our work to date. This includes highlighting some of the perspectives of our members, including publishers, publishing service providers, and library supporters, as well as our Collective Development Fund recipients and reviewers.

In many ways, then, this report is an evaluation, as the title suggests. But it is more than that. From the very start of our work on what would become the OBC, we have been seeking to listen to the diverse groups and communities whose support is, and will continue to be, vital for us and our members. In May 2021, we published a report based in part on surveys and workshops with UK and US-based librarians.³ From this, we established the core principles and aims that would inform the design of the OBC. We suggested that this as then unnamed organisation should:

¹ November 2019 to April 2023. Funded by the Research England Development Fund and Arcadia.

² May 2023 to April 2026. Funded by the same two funders.

³ Gerakopoulou, E., I. Penier, J. Deville (2021). The promise of collaboration: Collective funding models and the integration of Open Access books into libraries. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4501512>

1. 'harness the specific potential of collaboration across OA [open access] publishers , as a way of collectively funding publishing via a non-BPC [Book Processing Charge] based approach'
2. 'strengthen relationships between libraries and publishers. We have repeatedly observed the significant gap that exists between libraries and publishers'
3. 'collectively educate about OA. It is vital that OA publishers contribute towards the work of educating scholars and management within HEIs [Higher Education Institutions] about the potential benefits of supporting OA not just financially but also through publishing choices and teaching'

Fourth, and finally, the 2021 report also concluded that '[a] new model for OA book publishing cannot be based solely on the promise of funds being transferred from institutions to publishers. It needs to be supported by a robust funding mechanism that will make it sustainable in the long run'.

Looking back at these principles and aims nearly five years on, it is striking how closely we stuck to them. We have very much harnessed the potential of collaboration across OA publishers, alongside book publishing infrastructure providers. We operate – in name, in spirit, in practice – as a collective. We have brought libraries and publishers – and infrastructure providers – closer together, not just through the transfer of funds, but also in our governance, in the reports our members make available to libraries, in the collaborative events we have run. We have, with others, collectively educated: in a number of networks and contexts, the degree of understanding about the kind of alternative funding models the OBC advocates for are far more nuanced than they were when the 2021 report was written. But we have also listened: we understand the library landscape far more deeply now than we did back then, including the intricacies of library workflows, roles, and relations between the various metaorganisations and platforms that individual libraries depend upon. And finally, we have built a financial model which, at least in principle, will support the OBC as an organisation capable of sustaining itself into the long term. More on that later.

In many ways, then, the OBC's work has just begun. This report provides a detailed analysis of how stakeholders, from a range of contexts, have engaged with our work. And it concludes with insights into areas where we need to further focus our efforts. These include attending to the details of how we communicate with our stakeholders, including around both our processes and explaining the wider work we do, for example our Collective Development Fund grants. There is a strong desire from librarians for us to develop new resources to support them in making the case for our Diamond funding model internally. And some stakeholders see particular opportunities for us to further support the diverse and global open access community, by making the most of our relatively unique role as a collective, bringing together publishers, librarians, and fledging open research initiatives from around the world. This role provides opportunities for the OBC to deliver new forms of peer support, and to develop new open infrastructures to support this diverse community. And, as the analysis of our current

financial position shows, there is some work to be done to achieve not just ‘bare bones’ sustainability, but to be able to do all the things our stakeholders would like us to do. We are already working on responding to these insights and look forward to reporting on this further in due course.

However, what also comes through from across our stakeholders, from all respondent groups – libraries, publishers, publishing service providers, and Collective Development Fund recipients – is a clear endorsement of the work that we are doing. Our stakeholders broadly tell us that our values align closely with theirs and that our work is needed, that it is helpful, that it is having an impact – for example, on the volume of open access books they have capacity to publish, on their ability to hire staff to support this work, on the quality of metadata that accompanies their open access books, on the breadth of their digital dissemination. For an organisation that is still so relatively new, that is still learning, this is an achievement that should not be understated.

The analysis of our finances and sustainability model also simultaneously offers hope and outlines challenges. In many ways, we have achieved things that at the start of the COPIM project in 2019 seemed unthinkable. This includes securing potentially renewable subscriptions from close to 100 supporting libraries, which has succeeded in generating over £1.7million in funding commitments to OBC publisher and service provider members to date, almost 90% of which goes directly to these organisations or is used to support the wider open access book publishing ecosystem, via our Collective Development Fund annual grants programme. This success should not be underestimated. However, our analysis shows that the OBC needs to continue to sustain its current rate of growth over the coming years, and potentially exceed it, if it is to be able not just to continue to exist, but to flourish in what is currently a highly fragile higher education sector. This means, over the next three years, at a minimum, increasing to around 200 the number of libraries supporting our work, while also convincing them of the value of supporting a wider range of our publisher and service provider members.

In closing, I would like to offer my thanks to all those who have played a role in the OBC’s development. A full set of acknowledgements is included in Appendix 1, but this of course includes our two generous funders, Research England and Arcadia, all those who contributed to this report, as well as our library, publisher, and publishing service provider members. I am also deeply grateful to all those who have worked on and collaborated with the OBC on its path so far. Thanks to all this collaboration, it seems to me that the OBC has started to deliver on what once seemed just a speculative possibility: that a different way of engaging and collaborating around longform open access book publishing could be done. This alone is an achievement. But there is much work still to be done, to help deliver the deep changes in scholarly book publishing that are so urgently required.

Joe Deville, April 2026

1. Introduction

This report presents an evaluation of the OBC's activities and stakeholder engagement during its first years of operation, as well as reflections on OBC's future plans. As the charity moves towards a transition from primarily grant-based funding to a model fully sustained through library support, this evaluation provides an opportunity to reflect on how effectively the organisation has served the open access books community – including libraries, open access publishers, publishing service providers, and fledgling open access networks and initiatives – and how it might develop in the future.

The evaluation has two primary components. The first is an evaluation of how our work is understood and engaged with by our stakeholders, drawing on feedback from the key communities involved in the OBC's work: publisher and service provider members, library supporters, recipients of the Collective Development Fund, and the reviewers and panellists involved in assessing those grants. Through a combination of surveys and follow-up interviews, we have gathered perspectives on the benefits of participation with the OBC, areas where our work so far has had the most impact, and opportunities for improvement. The second is an analysis of OBC's current financial position and plans for post-project sustainability.

The sections that follow outline the methodology used in the stakeholder evaluation (Section 2), the findings from each stakeholder group (Sections 3 – 6), and the analysis of OBC finances (Section 7). The report concludes (Section 8) with reflections on the OBC's progress to date and identifies areas for further development as we move into our next phase.

2. Stakeholder Evaluation Methodology

In engaging with the different stakeholder groups, this evaluation used two primary methods: surveys and interviews.

2.1. Survey Methodology

Between October 2025 and January 2026, we designed and distributed surveys to the following discrete groups:

1. OBC publisher and service provider members
2. OBC library members (past and/or present)
3. Collective Development Fund awardees
4. Collective Development Fund panellists and reviewers

In each survey, we asked about respondents' experiences with:

- our communications and outreach
- the processes and operations relevant to the category of recipient
- what we have done well and what benefits recipients recognised
- how we can improve our services to the OA books community in line with our charitable objects

We received 12 responses from publisher and service provider members, 20 from current or former library members, 5 responses from Collective Development Fund (CDF) awardees; 12 from CDF panellists and reviewers. In most surveys we gave respondents the option of full anonymity (e.g. response attributed only to 'a publisher'), partial anonymity (e.g. response attributed to 'librarian at Example University') or being named, which has been honoured in the text below. However, CDF recipients have been identified in the survey responses, as their projects are already public information. We followed these surveys up with semi-structured interviews with a convenience sample of volunteers from each category in January, February and April 2026. In the interviews, we asked for more detailed narrative accounts of each participant's experiences with the OBC, especially on how we can improve and extend our work going forward. In these, we offered the option of anonymity to CDF recipients, who discussed processes more than their specific projects. The survey questions are attached as Appendix 2.⁴

2.2. Interview Methodology

⁴ This research was conducted in line with Lancaster University's Research Integrity Code of Practice, with the research having been granted ethical approval by the Faculty of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences and Lancaster University Management School joint Research Ethics Committee.

Between January and April 2026, we were able to complete follow up interviews with a selection of our survey respondents. Interviews were carried out and recorded and auto-transcribed by Microsoft Teams or Zoom. We spoke with 5 OBC publisher and service provider members, 2 reviewers and panellists for the CDF process, and 5 CDF recipients from the 2024 and 2025 rounds. Unfortunately, no librarian members volunteered for interview. In these semi-structured interviews, we utilised respondents' survey answers as prompts and asked them to elaborate on their thoughts. As above, respondents were given the option of full or partial anonymity or to be named in the outputs of this research, which has been honoured in our analysis. The direct quotations we use in the analysis have been lightly edited from speech for readability. Interviews were conducted by Francesca Corazza, Joe Deville, Judith Fathallah and Izabella Penier.

3. Publisher and Service Provider Member Feedback

3.1. Publisher and Service Provider Member Survey Responses

We conducted separate surveys for our library members and publisher and service provider members (see Appendix 2). Broadly, we asked our publisher and service provider members why they decided to join the OBC; how they found the process of joining; what benefits they have gained from it; and for feedback on how we could improve to better serve our members, charitable aims and the OA books community.

3.1.1. Reasons for Joining

Our publisher and service provider members primarily stated that they decided to join the OBC for three reasons: firstly, to gain a new revenue source enabling the publication of more OA work; secondly, due to perceived 'alignment in values around scholar/ community- led and governed infrastructure' (Urooj Nizami, PKP); and thirdly, to reduce the administrative burdens of securing funding:

We have been trying to find additional sources of income to support our work as we grow the Press's publishing programme and expand our activity in supporting open access publishing, and the OBC offered an important new intervention to support presses like ours. I also appreciated the alignment of our mission and values with the OBC's, particularly around collaboration, a commitment to bibliodiversity and care for high-quality, rigorous open access book publishing (Paula Kennedy, University of London Press).

We joined the OBC first because its values were (and remain) so consistent with our own. The community support model – tied to Diamond OA – is simply the superior mode for generating support for scholar-led publishing (Dave Park, mediastudies.press).

Reduction in administration seems particularly important for smaller publishers, and was consistently cited as a reason for joining:

At our scale, we do not have the capacity to approach many libraries directly to ask for OA publishing support; and likewise, most libraries do not have the bandwidth to deal with lots of small presses like us. So, setting up our own 'membership' model would not have been feasible. The OBC solves this by providing infrastructure that allows many small presses to aggregate their presence, and this simplifies the process of seeking and securing library support (James Rice, The White Horse Press).

One potential positive impact of OBC funding is that it has enabled conversations with consortia that, due to our size and fees, we wouldn't be able to join individually (Anonymous publisher).

We've received funding from over 35 institutions though the OBC who have shouldered the majority of the administrative burden, saving us time (Silke Davison, OAPEN).

One of the key benefits the OBC offers, therefore, is to enable small and medium-sized publishers and infrastructure providers who would not have the ability to set up or fully manage their own collective funding scheme to either participate in such a model or expand the support they receive from libraries.

3.1.2. Processes and Operations

Publishers and service providers acknowledged that the process of becoming a member is quite involved and does require a commitment in terms of time and labour. However, respondents understood that stringent, transparent processes and standards are necessary to the integrity of OBC's mission. The support, advice and technology involved on the OBC's side was commended by respondents, with one noting:

We had a lot of support both before and during the application process from Joe Deville and others at OBC, including feedback on draft submissions, which was extremely helpful. The OBC's processes and governance have been transparent from the start, and the OBC team has always dealt with our queries in an open and supportive way (Paula Kennedy, University of London Press).

Another 'found the materials provided and the support very helpful and positive' (Andreas Kirchner, meson press). However, one anonymous publisher asked for more clarification and guidance on the process of invoicing, and another experienced an administrative mix-up resulting in duplication of forms.

3.1.3. Benefits

One key benefit members identified was that OBC funds can be relatively flexibly deployed (in line with the OBC's purposes), as opposed to income from other sources – e.g. Book Processing Charges (BPCs), or alternative Diamond OA funding models – which are tied to the publication of particular texts. This flexibility was repeatedly described as important, with respondents citing a wide range of uses for OBC funding, including the ability to cross-subsidise publication of un(der)funded books and support under-resourced publishers:

A really important aspect of this [support] is that OBC funds can be allocated to book projects flexibly, where the funds are actually most needed. This lets us proceed on an OA basis with books that do not benefit from direct institutional support, or those projects that benefit from institutional support to a partial level only. OBC funds are thus very efficient in enabling OA production – more so than BPCs (James Rice, The White Horse Press).

Compared to other funding models, the flexibility of the funding has been a huge benefit for us. It enables us to take on additional books we otherwise wouldn't have been able to publish, and has also contributed to the staffing costs of a new part-time Editorial Assistant employed in our team to support both our growing publishing programme and the external free publishing training sessions we run. We have also used OBC funding to help cover the costs of us signing up with Thoth [Open Metadata], the metadata and dissemination platform, so our books will benefit from improved discoverability and higher-quality metadata (Paula Kennedy, University of London Press).

Income received through the OBC supports Thoth Open Metadata's work with under-resourced publishers – which is working to make their valuable contributions to the scholarly records visible and accessible that otherwise would have been far more difficult to do (Toby Steiner, Thoth Open Metadata).

Respondents elaborated on how OBC membership supports bibliodiversity by enabling publication of 'books that we would otherwise be unable to produce due to insufficient funding' (Andreas Kirchner, meson press) and/or that may not find a home in commercial series:

A little more than a year ago we published a book titled *Early Media Effects Theory & the Suggestion Doctrine: Selected Readings, 1895-1935* [...] I cannot imagine any other publisher putting out a book like this. It simply does not link up with any fashionable idea in media studies right now. But now that it has been out for more than a year, it is finding an audience. It is getting absorbed into the bibliographies of the field and it has real promise for shaping the ongoing sense of the intellectual history of media studies. It was OBC funding that made that possible. Perhaps this is how scholarly publishing should always work. Of course this is how scholarly publishing should always work. Without OBC funding, it would not have happened (Dave Park, mediastudies.press).

Participants also noted the importance of the non-monetary, community-based and knowledge-sharing benefits that OBC membership confers, explaining that the process of becoming a member has, for example, sparked important internal conversations around initiatives' own work and missions. One member noted that they 'benefit from a close working relationship with colleagues at OBC, working on projects, events, and outreach planning together' (Silke Davison, OAPEN). One publisher has learned 'more about the wishes and needs of library supporters with regard to the financing of Diamond OA' (Andreas Kirchner, meson.press) through becoming a member. Others stated,

non-monetary support, for example around navigating the technical challenges around emerging accessibility standards, has been invaluable. There's a sense that the OBC tried to create value by generating a sense of community among its members, and this is really good to be part of (James Rice, The White Horse Press).

We are immensely grateful for all the support provided by OBC staff, and the fantastic opportunities to exchange knowledge with other participants across the different caucuses (Toby Steiner, [Thoth Open Metadata](http://ThothOpenMetadata)).

It has also always been important to us that the OBC administrators have been such upstanding people, so friendly and easy to work with. We would like for the OBC admin to know that we are grateful for who they are as people (Dave Park, mediastudies.press).

The importance of OBC's broader charitable purpose to support public access to scholarship was also noted, as

Another really positive impact is on readership. Our OA publications attract far higher usage levels than our gated publications, so the more we publish OA, the more impact we and our authors have on the wider discourse. This is an unalloyed positive (James Rice, The White Horse Press).

Finally, survey respondents noted reputational gains both inside and outside of their home institutions:

[Membership] strengthens the Press's position internally – we can demonstrate to senior managers that we are actively diversifying funding streams and that we are shifting away from a full reliance on university budgets (an important message to demonstrate especially as a non-profit Press that doesn't fit a traditional UP model) and that libraries of eminent HEIs are investing in us, which demonstrates our wider value to the community [...] [It also] raises our profile externally – I would hope that membership helps raise our profile amongst libraries/institutions globally who may use [our] Press publications as a result or recommend [our] Press as a potential publisher to their academics (Anonymous Publisher).

A broader positive impact from receiving OBC funding is our ability to demonstrate that we can diversify our income stream to our host university. In this current moment of financial crisis in universities globally, this is a hugely important benefit of our involvement with OBC. Being able to demonstrate financial support from external libraries globally for our work as a publisher to our university's senior management team helps us to

make the case for continued support. It also helps our longer-term sustainability, our visibility with colleagues within our university, and raises awareness of non-BPC funding models across the university (Paula Kennedy, University of London Press).

3.1.4. Improvements

In terms of improvements the OBC could make, it was requested that we increase our communication with publisher and service provider members, and increase the number of collaborative events for our community:

The library/publisher forum meetings are a very useful opportunity to come together as a group to exchange information and learn about the pressures and opportunities from both sides. I'd welcome this being a more regular meeting, and perhaps to explore wider discussion of how both parties might collaborate on shared messaging around non-BPC models for OA to different audience (Paula Kennedy, University of London Press).

I would be interested in considering in-person opportunities to get together around activities like a sprint that may be attached to other in-person events that will have high participation from OBC members (Urooj Nizami, PKP).

While the monthly statements have developed and improved since I first started receiving them, sometimes it's difficult to reconcile the support we've received with the remittance advice and matching it with the correct year/date period. Perhaps an annual statement would be useful too (Silke Davison, OAPEN).

Part of this communication could be connected to profile-raising on behalf of publishers both internally and externally, as one suggested:

I would welcome any opportunities via OBC's networks/work to raise the profile of [our] Press generally, specifically to encourage new book proposals/authors to approach us. This could be done for all publisher members who are actively open for proposals. Help/guidance/best practice advice on how to discuss our model with senior managers or explain the value we bring (both financial and beyond) to our home institution would be useful, especially in continuing to make the case in times of financial crisis (Anonymous Publisher).

One newer member noted that anticipated benefits are yet to materialise, stating 'I'm still vague on whether we might see a visible income stream sufficient to publish one or more books through OBC funds within a year, or two years, or longer' (Anonymous Publisher). Becoming an OBC member is not a guarantee that libraries will sign up to support a particular initiative, as this is decided ultimately by the library members themselves. One anonymous respondent asked if the application process could be further streamlined, and another suggested we reconsider how OBC funds are distributed:

We think it would make sense to reconsider how OBC determines the distribution of funds across its affiliate publishers. Though this process was developed in a manner that was inclusive and drew input from all of us, we can see how the distribution of funds seems to have created some inequities between publishers (Dave Park, mediastudies.press).

Another publisher recommended that we further internationalise our operations (Andreas Kirchner, meson press), specifically beyond the UK, US and Europe. Finally, it was suggested that 'we should consider broadening our horizons for financial support' beyond libraries, 'to offices of research and other adjacent stakeholders who undoubtedly have a mandate to support research outputs' (Urooj Nizami, PKP). This is certainly an avenue the OBC intends to explore in the future.

3.2. Publisher and Service Provider Members Interview Responses

From our publisher and service provider membership, we interviewed Silke Davison, Community Manager at OAPEN, Toby Steiner, COO of Thoth Open Metadata, Paula Kennedy from University of London Press, a representative from Open Book Publishers who chose partial anonymity, and another publisher who chose to remain anonymous.

3.2.1. Reasons for Joining and Associated Benefits

Respondents generally discussed their reasons for joining the OBC and the benefits they derived from it together. Some of these were administrative, with speakers elaborating on the time and labour involved in running a small initiative:

It's amazing that I can take a little bit of my workload and put it on the OBC, and they can help me with that. [With] invoices to make and libraries to follow up, it [does] help me quite a lot when it comes to time management (Representative from Open Book Publishers).

We rely predominantly on library support to sustain our operations. So, having an agent who can help us find that support, and also manage the administrative side of things saves us time as well [...] it saves us having to reach out individually to all these institutions for renewals (Silke Davison, OAPEN).

Relatedly, interviewees elaborated on the importance of OBC as a collective resource, a facilitator, and a mark of initiative quality in a busy and fragmented OA landscape:

[We thought it was] a good idea to sort of find a place in which all our libraries can assess not only ourselves, but also other open access initiatives [...] one of the things that was brought to me quite a lot when I had meetings with libraries was that they didn't know much about the open access landscape, and they didn't know where to start, which is amazing [...] It's not only [Open Book Publishers], there are a lot of open access initiatives that are worth checking, and you have one place when you can go and find them (Representative from Open Book Publishers).

Interviewees also elaborated on mission alignment, value fit, and being part of the OBC community, demonstrating how these factors intersect for members in practice:

I think we decided to join the OBC because we see the value in the collective funding model, and the obvious benefit of increased visibility, and then gaining more support from libraries [...] Also, through membership we are able to support the OBC and contribute to initiatives like the Collective Development Fund. Supporting other open access book initiatives is important so we can show that we can work well together and interoperate (Silke Davison, OAPEN).

Participants also expanded on the direct benefits that came from membership, including being able to increase the number of open access books a publisher could produce, undertake wider work in the sector to support that work, with OBC funding also providing additional financial security:

It helps my [colleague] to be able to spend more time on training and advocacy work about open access and publishing generally. So that's been a key thing. It's helped us to be able to commission a few more books and know that we've got this extra support to do that. One of the challenges of being a smaller university press is that you're very reliant on funding from your institution, which usually has to be negotiated year on year. To have just a little bit extra that you can use for things like signing up with Thoth, for example, which wasn't in our original budget but that we could use OBC funding towards (Paula Kennedy, University of London Press).

When it comes to Thoth Open Metadata, staff discussed how they have been working with us collaboratively throughout the development of the OBC, including on our membership criteria and governance structure. This is in part because Thoth is an organisation that, like the OBC, emerged out of the first Copim project. Toby Steiner told us that

From Thoth's perspective, we were really excited to see how well all of this aligned with the community-led approach that we've been living through the Copim project [...] so I think we were thrilled to be part of the of the initiative from the get go and highly supportive also from the technical standpoint because of the OBC's valuing of open source, open data and all those open principles, which of course are also very much key tenets of what Thoth is doing (Toby Steiner, Thoth Open Metadata).

For Thoth, as a relatively new initiative, the OBC provides a major source of financial support. We discussed particularly how this flexible source of revenue enables Thoth to support the work of under-resourced publishers outside of the Global North, in keeping with our commitment to bibliodiversity:

More and more publishers have approached Thoth coming from under-resourced regions of the world [...] applications to join Thoth from the Latin American space, for example, from Africa, and some of those we've been able to support without charging them any kind of fees that would be required to cover the work, and that's really thanks to the support that we are getting through libraries from the OBC (Toby Steiner, Thoth Open Metadata).

The OBC's assistance in outreach is appreciated, as we may have more or different capacity to reach institutions than individual publishers and service providers. Many small publishers simply do not have the capacity to operate their own membership scheme, and moreover, their scale would probably not render them attractive for individual support. The OBC is also able to approach and negotiate with consortia to support our packages or indeed the entire Collective:

The OBC has reached libraries that, for different reasons, we weren't able to reach [...] You explain everything very clearly, and you present the idea, and present the publishers. [This] has convinced a few libraries that were a little bit harder to get for us, [for example] because the OBC is in conversation or in agreement with different library consortia (Representative from Open Book Publishers).

Agreements with library consortia may be harder to negotiate for small independent publishers than a collective of the OBC's size and diversity. Overall, interviewees were enthusiastic about working with the OBC: one anonymous publisher wanted to stress that 'my message is, I'm absolutely delighted with the partnership. I think it's fantastic. I'm so excited to be part of it'.

3.2.2. Processes and Operations

The members we interviewed generally found our onboarding and application process unremarkable and smooth. Reflecting on how Thoth colleagues, as project collaborators, could help refine our onboarding processes, Toby Steiner commented that

It was exciting to see because we could provide input into how that onboarding process could be streamlined, could be improved, could be kept at a low level because I think all of us agreed that we wouldn't want to make too much of a hassle of this formal process, so to keep it lightweight for stakeholders and infrastructures to join, but also of course there would be some due diligence that would be needed to adhere to and key information that needs to be collected (Toby Steiner, Thoth Open Metadata).

However, one potential process issue was flagged in discussion. When a potential supporter could take part in both an OBC package that includes a publisher or service provider and/or that publisher or service provider's own membership scheme, complications can arise:

We've had a couple of instances where the fees are slightly different if libraries support us directly [...] But even though fees for support through the OBC can be slightly higher, it enables libraries are able to embody the values they promote internally too (Silke Davison, OAPEN).

This interview also suggested that the downside of the OBC's reducing administrative labour is the potential for less oversight from the publisher or service provider:

Sometimes, from my side, not having as much control over the renewals is tricky [...] often I'm not sure what the status is with a lot of the [OBC] support, whereas with our other supporters, I can go directly to them (Silke Davison, OAPEN).

Similarly, another publisher stated they were 'not quite clear on the cycle' of invoicing and remittance, particularly when gaining new subscribers, and that they would like a clearer picture of how much money they held in OBC 'pots' at a given moment, and that an annual report on their financial status with regard to the OBC would be useful (Anonymous Publisher).

3.2.3. Improvements

The interviews elaborated on the requests for more frequent communications from the OBC that we saw in the survey data, with participants asking to receive information and updates on agreements with libraries as soon as possible (Representative from OBP). Members said this would help avoid miscommunication or overlap in outreach: 'there's sometimes a bit of a difficulty communicating when we want to reach out to people. Because we are reaching out to people, but you're also reaching out to people on our behalf (Davison). More regular communications and updates could be achieved by email or even live events: 'I think it's actually nice getting us to come together and hear from you and also hear from each other' (Davison). Joint workshops and/or webinars with publishers and service providers were suggested, as was co-producing literature to coordinate outreach work collectively. This was particularly stressed regarding renewals processes – it seems fair to say some publisher members would like a clearer and more regular oversight of the different stages in the renewals processes. One anonymous publisher asked if it was possible for the OBC to do more profile-raising of presses to librarians and authors, including at live events, but recognised the fine balance in that OBC is a collective rather than a directly transactional model of support. We discussed whether the OBC might play more of a role in matching presses and librarians with prospective authors, which could benefit and raise the profile of all involved. This interviewee also saw a role for the OBC in working with presses on internal advocacy within institutions, to help them 'show qualitatively and quantitatively that we are an important thing for the university to fund', demonstrating for example impact on dissemination and the value of supporting open access for universities in general (Anonymous Publisher). Further, Toby Steiner suggested that the OBC could work on a strand of outreach dedicated specifically to infrastructure providers and gaining more support for the crucial services they provide in the

OA space: acquisitions librarians may be less interested in these communications, but library directors could be an appropriate avenue of approach.

3.3. Reflections and Recommendations

It is clear from both the survey and interview feedback that the OBC is meeting a central part of its mission: supporting under-resourced, mission-aligned publishers/service providers, and strengthening bibliodiversity. We are also encouraged that publishers and service providers are experiencing non-monetary benefits (strengthened reputation, increased understanding of OA workflows, knowledge exchange), which shows that OBC participation has impact beyond financial support. These responses underscore the importance of the OBC community, signalling that the collective model successfully supports collaboration rather than competition, in accordance with our key values.

The publisher and service provider interview responses reinforce and deepen the survey findings, particularly around the importance of financial support, administrative relief, collective visibility, and mission alignment as drivers of publisher and service provider engagement. The interviews also underscore the symbolic and reputational value of OBC membership. Beyond financial support, the OBC functions as a signal of quality and legitimacy in a fragmented OA landscape, particularly for smaller initiatives that may struggle to articulate their value individually. With further funding, we could develop this important function, assisting publishers in demonstrating the internal value of an OA press in terms legible to budget holders. The prominence given to outreach via consortia further suggests that OBC's scale and diversity provide strategic advantages that individual members could not easily replicate on their own.

The responses also clearly highlight areas that need attention: the reported uncertainty about predictability of income suggests some misalignment between expectations and the model. And what emerges more clearly in the interviews than the surveys is a small trade-off inherent in the delegation of outreach work by providers to the OBC, especially those with their own pre-existing Diamond open access funding model: while reducing administrative labour is widely valued, it can also create moments of reduced visibility or perceived loss of control for members, especially around renewals and financial tracking. This tension does not appear to undermine confidence in OBC's model, but it does highlight the importance of clear, regular communication and shared oversight mechanisms.

Recommendations for the future that the OBC could action are as follows:

- Increase regularly scheduled email communication and improve documentation on matters like the status of library renewals, invoicing processes, and annual summaries of financial flows.
- Create more opportunities for collaboration, including events, workshops, or sprints connected to sector gatherings.

- Provide materials such as concise one-pagers to explain OBC membership to senior leadership.
- Design an improved onboarding process for new members, including video calls, better setting expectations regarding income.
- Develop outreach beyond the UK, US and Europe with a view to further internationalising our membership and operations and serving the international OA books community more effectively.

4. Library Member Feedback

4.1. Library Member Survey Responses

We first asked our library members how they heard about the OBC, which helps us understand the effectiveness of our outreach and communications work. We then asked their reasons for joining, and relatedly, what librarians consider the most important parts of the OBC's operations. As with our publisher and service provider members, we asked what benefits librarians derive from membership and how the OBC could improve our services. We also asked how our outreach to potential library members could be improved.

4.1.1. Outreach and Communications

Respondents stated either that they had been contacted during our direct outreach campaign (in person or by email), or that they had learned of us via professional networks, webinars, and listmails and communication from consortia like RLUK (Research Libraries UK), as well as personal contacts in the OA book sphere. Speaking at library-focused conferences was recommended as a key to increased support. One librarian noted that

The OBC is always very present at conferences and within the wider sector, the advocacy and outreach work the OBC does for these funding models is really valuable to support a wider uptake. It is becoming increasingly difficult to justify spend on OA initiatives within our budgets so this work does help with making the case for these activities (Anonymous Librarian).

One librarian learned of us through a blog post by one of our publisher members. One librarian commented that "from my perspective OBC has been very successful in promoting itself without "overselling"" (anonymous Librarian).

4.1.2. Reasons for Joining and the Importance of the OBC

Most members cited alignment with our model and values and mission as key reasons for joining:

Several years ago we developed some guiding principles for collection development. These placed an increased emphasis on things like sustainability, affordability, openness and equity when making purchasing decisions. OBC has made it easy to identify initiatives that we can support that align with these principles (Anna Franca, Edge Hill University).

We believe that Book Processing Charges are problematic for many reasons and want to support a diverse landscape of publishing activities that are free at the point of use to authors and readers (Anonymous Librarian).

As academic library staff, we are actively working to help shift the scholarly publishing system through education of our community and by supporting initiatives that truly work to transform to a more sustainably and equitable publishing ecosystem. The mission and community governance model of OBC is a strong fit (Anonymous Librarian).

Several participants noted that whilst they supported the OBC's mission and values, they also wished to provide high quality Diamond OA options for authors at their own institutions. Of

course, authors do not have to be a member of a subscribing institution to publish with our members, but membership raises their profile and acts as a guarantee of quality for prospective authors, due to our membership standards.

We asked librarians what they considered the most important examples of OBC's work. Responses were rich and diverse, and addressed many parts of the OBC's mission. They included:

1. OBC's support for Diamond OA books and infrastructure, as 'publicly funded research outputs should be publicly available without (high) additional costs' (Anonymous Librarian)
2. Relatedly, OBC's demonstration of a sustainable OA model and showcase of relevant publishers, particularly for Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (Anonymous Librarians)
3. OBC's support of infrastructure and a bibliodiverse landscape, including smaller publishers (Anonymous Librarians)
4. OBC's quality standards, such as 'high quality metadata and in different formats' as 'it's important that Diamond OA publications adhere to best practices regarding metadata so that there is no shortcoming in comparison to for-profit-publishers' (Librarian at Goethe University), allowing our offerings to stand out amongst an extremely high volume of email offerings (Anonymous Librarian)
5. OBC's position as an umbrella body for different publishers and infrastructure providers, which 'streamlines the invoicing and payment process' (Anonymous Librarian) for libraries and 'raise(s) visibility and enable(s) coordination' (Anonymous Librarian)
6. The Collective Development Fund and its help for small publishers (Anonymous Librarians)
7. OBC's work in the Global South (Librarian at Institute of Art, Design and Technology)

4.1.3. Benefits

In terms of direct benefits to institutions, some libraries noted the importance of additional offerings provided by publishers to library supporters, such as free additional digital formats of books, or discounts on hard copies. Connected with the above answer, one stressed the ease of discovering high quality initiatives:

The OBC has allowed [us] to discover and support a number of smaller scholar-led open access publishers in a streamlined and efficient way. We have also been able to support open access infrastructure. The benefit for us is that we can actively support genuine OA initiatives, and this aligns with (and has fed into the creation of) our OA collection development policy (Anonymous Librarian).

However, when reflecting on the benefits for libraries in collaborating with the OBC, librarians most frequently cited how OBC helped streamline the administrative burden of supporting multiple initiatives:

[The OBC] makes it much easier to invest time and funding in initiatives, when we can direct these through an existing body, rather than trying to act unilaterally. Without OBC, we would simply not have the time or expertise to engage. Also, it enables us to demonstrate that support of open monograph publishing is part of a wider collaborative and strategic framework, giving a stronger rationale for continuing investment (Anonymous Librarian).

OBC makes it easy to support several initiatives with moderate administrative effort (Anonymous Librarian).

Several of the open book initiatives that my institution was already supporting (e.g., OBP, punctum) were moving under the OBC umbrella. We contacted a few of those organizations to inquire whether they wanted their supporters to continue to fund directly or switch to supporting them via OBC. They all wanted supporters to move to OBC, so we did! (Anonymous Librarian).

One anonymous librarian found it ‘easier to make the case once [internally] for supporting this type of scheme rather than repeatedly making the case to support each individual offer. It also introduced to us new initiatives / publishers we could support that I was not aware of previously’. Other benefits noted included ‘being part of the community governance/communications’ which ‘helps me have a deeper understanding of open book publishing’ (Anonymous Librarian), and the ability to show Library support for ‘researchers in Art, Humanities and Social Science subjects by helping them publish open access long-form outputs in a sustainable way’ (Anonymous Librarian). Relatedly, some respondents noted that membership raises the visibility of options for Diamond OA publishing within their institution (Anonymous Librarians). Importantly, one anonymous participant expressed feeling satisfied with ‘the main benefits of OBC being more indirect, long-term ones (investing in a more sustainable, equitable OA publication landscape)’. Looking to the long term, one participant added,

I hope the support for non-BPC models will make some contribution to maintaining/increasing diverse business models in publishing OA books, which will help Universities financially in the long term as BPCs are not sustainable at scale (Anonymous Librarian).

4.1.4. Improvements

In terms of how we can improve our service to library members, several answers echoed the concerns of the librarians we surveyed in our report on barriers to collective funding models for librarians in diverse European contexts,⁵ noting the severe financial pressures being experienced by many higher education institutions, globally. These answers centered on the need for libraries to be provided with data with which to justify their support for the OBC:

⁵ Fathallah, J., J. Deville, I. Penier, F. Corazza (2025). Collective funding models for open access books: Librarians' experiences and barriers to participation across six European contexts. *Open Book Collective*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17339946>

Library members need to justify their expenditure, particularly so in times of financial hardship. Any facts/figures (e.g. books published by affiliated academics, downloads) that OBC can pass on to help build business cases would be very useful (Anonymous Librarian)

It would be great to hear an update from OBC (webinar or similar) that shares information on how library membership has supported the different OBC presses/initiatives and future growth plans. As library budgets continue to shrink it could become harder for libraries to justify expenditure on initiatives like OBC when difficult decisions need to be made (Anna Franca, Edge Hill University).

I would like to see more updates from the providers we are supporting, e.g. a regular newsletter with details of what our financial contributions are funding, what difference our support makes, so we can see some tangible outcomes of the scheme - and use these to make the case for continuing support (Anonymous Librarian).

Librarians asked for guidance and tools to make the case to budget holders for continued support. Building on the theme of working with and supporting researchers, one respondent suggested OBC working on

specific initiatives that lean in to librarian expertise and have a clear beginning and end/output...having materials targeted to our faculty/authors about the benefits of OA publishing would be helpful – how to work with the OBC publishers – what topics editors are looking for would be helpful as a kind of full circle benefit (Anonymous Librarian).

One anonymous participant found that navigating between publishers on our website could be a little confusing. Overall, though, the OBC was commended as an ‘impressive, inclusive operation’ (Librarian at Institute of Art, Design and Technology). One respondent urged,

Keep going, keep getting out there, keep convincing institutional leaders that this is what truly sustainable development looks like in publishing (not the nonsense of commercial publishers, who mean ‘continued sources of profit for us’ when they say ‘sustainable’) (Anonymous Librarian).

4.2. Reflections and Recommendations

A significant motivation for libraries to join the OBC is their own alignment with our key values, especially the importance of supporting Diamond OA. Librarians value inclusive governance, mission alignment and bibliodiversity, suggesting that initiatives like the OBC can succeed in part by appealing to mission and values alignment, although librarians suggest that this needs to be backed up by concrete data to support cases internally. Many find OBC an administrative simplifier, making it easy to support multiple high-quality initiatives through one community-led platform, which is valued. The fact that librarians noted how membership shows support for AHSS researchers and raises the profile of Diamond OA publishing is promising for the development of author outreach and education within institutions, which the OBC and broader Copim networks are already beginning to engage in. This is an important strand of work that could be taken up with further grant funding, via the establishment of cross-institutional hubs for Diamond OA publishing specifically involving researchers at all stages of their careers. Improvements the OBC could action are as follows:

- Provide more metrics to libraries (e.g. citations from/by local researchers, publications by local researchers, local usage data).

- Provide outreach materials to support internal advocacy, including clearer messaging for faculty and senior managers and evidence for business cases as well as advocacy materials for researchers.
- Provide more structured engagement opportunities for AHSS researchers in institutions, for example helping facilitate researcher interactions with OBC publishers, their authors, and/or OBC's wider networks.

5. Collective Development Fund Awardee Feedback

5.1. Introducing the Collective Development Fund

A key aim of the OBC is to support publishers, infrastructure providers and other organisations to build capacity to increase the quantity, quality and diversity of open access books. One way it does this is by awarding grants from its Collective Development Fund (CDF).

To date, the CDF has been funded via two routes: directly, from funders, via the OBF project and from contributions made by our publisher and service provider members. OBC publishers and publishing service providers are invited to allocate 5% of the Supporter Programme revenue they are due from subscribers to the CDF, something they almost all choose to do. The end of the OBF project means that the CDF will, for the foreseeable future, be wholly funded via this second route.

The Fund supports work that builds capacity for open access scholarly books in one or more of three priority areas:

- Creating and supporting infrastructures and/or workflows for the distribution, cataloguing and/or preservation of open access scholarly books.
- Building and sustaining networks and advocacy for the support of OA scholarly books and infrastructure.
- Projects building capacity for scholarly OA book publishing.

The Fund does not support costs directly associated with the production of specific scholarly publications, for example Book Processing Charges (BPCs). Each year, we aim to allocate at least a third of the total available funds to recipients and projects based in Lower and Middle Income Countries (LMICs), as defined by the World Bank. We also offer an optional scope check for a limited period prior to submission of a full application, in order for applicants to assess whether their proposed project is or could be eligible for the Fund (for a brief summary of projects funded so far, see Appendix 3).⁶

We currently offer the Call, guidance, and applications forms in English, Spanish, Portuguese and French, with French being a new addition for the 2025 round. However, English and Spanish submissions have dominated the applications received so far.

Table 5.1 shows the number and type of applications received, progressed and funded for each round so far (data for 2026 is incomplete as the Call is ongoing at the time of writing).

⁶ Updates on the work accomplished by the projects can be found on the dedicated section of the OBC news portal: <https://obc.copim.pub/collective-development-fund/>

Table 5.1: Number and type of CDF applications

Year	2024	2025	2026
Number of scope checks	19	6	33
Number of applications	35	13	59
Number progressed to external review	8	6	10
Number progressed from LMICs	6	6	7
Number funded	3	4	
Number funded from LMICs	2	4	
Progressed applications in English	7	3	
Progressed applications in Spanish	1	3	
Progressed applications in French	N/A	0	
Progressed applications in Portuguese	0	0	
Progressed applications for up to £7,500	2	1	
Progressed applications for up to £15,000	6	5	
Funded applications for up to £7,500	1	1	
Funded applications for up to £15,000	2	3	

5.2. Collective Development Fund Awardee Survey Results

We asked CDF awardees for feedback on how they found the process of application; the importance and impact of the CDF; the monitoring and reporting procedures. We also asked how participants learned about the Call; and how we might expand our outreach around it in the future.

5.2.1. Outreach and Communications

Participants learned about the scheme from diverse sources, including emails sent via mailing lists, social media, professional networks, conferences/workshops in applicants' own geographic context organised by or featuring OBC, as well as via word of mouth. Here is worth noting that especially in African and Latin American contexts, the OBC has been supported by various individuals and organisations such as University of Cape Town Libraries, WACREN (West and Central African Research and Education Network) and SciELO Books. For example, participants told us:

I attended an open access book publishing workshop in Cape Town in 2025 where the fund was talked about (Josiline Chigwada, 2024 Recipient).

I got to know about CDF through the network of Wacren and Libsense in Nigeria (Abdulsalami Kovo, 2024 Recipient).

I heard about the CDF through word of mouth from my co-lead on the project that was funded (Kath Burton, 2024 Recipient).

Another recipient referenced a newsletter from the Asociación de Editoriales Universitarias de América Latina y el Caribe (EULAC; in English, Association of University Presses of Latin America and the Caribbean) (Catalina del Mar Garrido Torres, 2025 Recipient).

5.2.2. Processes and Operations

The process of applying was found to be simple and efficient, with applicants finding it ‘easy to follow’ (Josiline Chigwada) with one noting, ‘the application process was seamless and every stage was with clarity. There is quick feedback for every question and concern’ (Abdulsalami Kovo). A third recipient found,

The application process was very clear and provided useful guidance on how to apply. The structured approach made it possible to craft a clear outline and ensure that we met the criteria for the call (Kath Burton).

My experience with the application process was smooth and straightforward. The instructions were clear, and the required documents were easy to upload. Overall, it was well-organized (Tilahun Shiferaw).

The application process is very precise, has clear instructions and the option of having a first evaluation, with the general idea, is very useful [...] the OBC professionals were very kind and very willing to answer any question about the application process (Catalina del Mar Garrido Torres).

This recipient also suggested that we ‘could provide, for example, a more accurate idea of the scope of the project according to the budget that will be requested’. Most recipients found the reporting and monitoring processes satisfactory and effective, noting that they ‘keep the conversation going between the funder and the fundee’ (Josiline Chigwada), and ‘the reporting system has been very good with good time given to grantees to prepare for the reporting’ (Abdulsalami Kovo). One considered the ‘reporting requirements [to be] coherent with the aim of the OBC fund for promoting bibliodiversity and the publishing of open access’ (Catalina del Mar Garrido Torres). However, another found the reporting requirements to be more onerous given the timezone differences and suggested that asynchronous communication might be easier. This participant also suggested provision of reporting forms to be filled out at the start of the project, ‘that would help us draw out simple items to report at intervals during the year’ (Kath Burton).

5.2.3. Impact

On the impact and importance of the Fund, recipients noted that they have been able to make significant progress with their projects, which can also be viewed on the OBC blog. They told us:

The funding provided us with some necessary time to gather and focus ideas around the concept of community publishing. This concept resonated with our participants, but also rippled out to others adjacent to the project [...] who wanted to better understand and apply some of the ideas we had posed. This has resulted in one additional event being held [...]. The event opened up a number of opportunities to review the community publishing concept, not least in relation to any workflows and processes we had imagined emerging from the project (Kath Burton).

We have managed to provide the infrastructure needed for open access book publishing as well as capacity building among the writers, reviewers, and librarians (Josiline Chigwada).

One of the outstanding successes of the CDF in our case is the establishment of community of authors determined to open access book publishing and utilization of the bookhub platform which facilitate collaborative authoring making book publishing workflow simple (Abdulsalami Kovo).

One recipient noted,

Our project is about to start, nonetheless, the idea of creating a web between smalls and mediums institutions of the Southwest region in Colombia has been received with great enthusiasm. We did the first round of visits to some of the institutions to specify the inter-institutional agreements and to start the characterization of necessities and capacities where we found a great diversity, with surely will go to enrich this project (Catalina del Mar Garrido Torres).

2025 awardees have just begun their work, so further developments will be publicised by the OBC in due course.

5.2.4. Improvements

On the question of how we could improve awareness of the programme, it was suggested that the OBC use ‘ambassadors to talk about the fund in conferences, meetings, and webinars’ (Josiline Chigwada), as well as our usual strategy of employing mailing lists and relevant social media platforms. One recipient noted,

We had hoped to connect with other CDF recipients during the course of the project, but did not manage to do so. I wonder if that might be something OBC could facilitate in order to broaden existing networks and spread the news about the types of projects being funded? (Kath Burton).

It was also suggested that in future we could increase the amount of funding available. Of course, this remains something we are eager to do, however it depends on our ability to secure sufficient contributions from our publisher and service provider members. For now, while the CDF grants remain relatively small (up to £15,000 for the larger grants), the work achieved with them is continuing to accomplish significant impact.

Finally, it was suggested that we could create ‘public feedback areas to share experiences and results such as forums or webinars, which helps build trust and encourages new applicants’ and that ‘it would be nice to present some books or manuals that are the results of the projects sponsored by CDF, in coherence with publishing practices of open access’ (Catalina del Mar Garrido Torres).

5.3. Collective Development Fund Awardee Interview Responses

We were able to interview five recipients of CDF awards: Kath Burton (co-lead of ‘The Community Publishing Garden’, funded 2024), Catalina del Mar Garrido Torres (co-lead of ‘Capacity building strategy for access and publication of Open Access academic books for small and medium-sized Higher Education Institutions in Southwestern Colombia’, funded 2025), Maria Fernanda Papin (co-lead of ‘Knowledge Accessible to the Community: CLACSO as a Platform to Democratize Scholarly Publishing in Latin America and the Caribbean’, funded 2025) and two who chose to remain anonymous for purposes of the interview. All projects are summarised in Appendix 3.

5.3.1. Application and Administration

In the interviews, we learned that CDF Calls have travelled further than we imagined, being shared in stakeholder WhatsApp and Telegram groups and listed on sites compiling funding for NGOs, and through a EULAC (Network of University Presses of Latin America) bulletin. Torres elaborated that when she learned of the Call, her institution was already practicing open access publishing, and was seeking to strengthen its publishing and research activities without charging fees. Key OBC principles – such as a commitment to bibliodiversity and the democratisation of knowledge – resonated with the university’s social and community-oriented vision. Papin added that CLASCO was motivated to apply by having previously learned of Copim at open access summits in Toluca, Mexico and Cape Town, South Africa, recognising the organisation as a European open access leader. Another recipient learned of the Call at the OBC’s workshop at the University of Cape Town in early 2024, noting:

I knew that this could be a positive development, especially for us in the developing countries. We face mainly the issue of resources to buy the required software, etcetera for us to be able to publish Open Access [...] If you look at the publishers that are there currently [in my country], they are only concentrating with publishing hard copies. There are no publishers that are publishing ebooks, especially for higher education, and also [none] publishing e-books in in in a local language (Grant Recipient).

The Call’s focus on bibliodiversity and equity were thus encouraging to the applicant. Papin told us that being able to read and apply in Spanish was an important enabling factor for CLACSO. Recipients confirmed in interviews that the application process was clear and accessible, which encouraged them to apply. Particularly commended was the description of the process and timeline:

The description of how the decision making was going to be handled was really clear and that made it really encouraging actually to pursue the full application. Because sometimes when I’m looking at applications, it’s really very unclear what the decision making process is going to be, what stages there might be in place, and as an applicant just gives you a real sense of unsurety about how long this is going to take in terms of once you put your application in and where you might be in the mix given all of the different variables and the people that might be evaluating (Kath Burton).

Another recipient commended our policy of keeping applicants up to date by email of the different stages their application is passing through. Applicants thought the forms were clear, simple and offered about the right amount of space to explain their project:

The required documents like the proposal and the financial [documents], the budget and the templates and everything is clear (Grant Recipient).

We really enjoyed applying. In some cases you might find a huge form where they'll be asking for a lot of information and it will take you days, weeks to just to fill in the form. But this one, it was different. It was very, very particular. You knew what you wanted from the grantees in this way (Grant Recipient).

The optional scope check, wherein applicants could first submit a 'brief project idea' for feedback on eligibility was viewed very positively and considered 'key' (Catalina del Mar Garrido Torres). For Papin, the OBC management team's feedback on framing the bid here was of critical importance to their success. She commended the OBC team's support throughout the application process. In the 2025 round, grantees thought that our publicised examples of previous projects were useful as guidance. The scope check and ease of downloading the application form also assisted an applicant in ensuring support from her institution.

One 2024 interviewee thought that the frequency and duration of reporting calls was about right and beneficial for both grantee and funder, but another again noted that arranging them could be difficult given the timezone differences across the project participants. We have already created budget templates for our 2025 awardees: project diaries, commitment registers and milestone trackers were also suggested by Kath Burton. Papin suggested a more explicit framework for mapping budget to activities and outputs, in order that the scope of projects for the differing amounts of funding offered be clearer.

5.3.2. Impact

Recipients elaborated on the impact of OBC funds so far. For 2025 recipients, this is at an early stage. Nonetheless, we learned that in the case of 'Capacity building strategy for access and publication of Open Access academic books for small and medium-sized Higher Education Institutions in Southwestern Colombia', the project has generated high expectations and reception amongst partner universities has been very positive, with enthusiasm and a willingness to collaborate. Another 2025 recipient stated that

the open book concept is very new [...] in my country. People, most of the time people just write a book for commercial purpose only [...] And in my project one of my work areas is advocacy. I tried to meet with some of the authors. We discussed some things regarding the open book concept. I asked them to have some of their books translated multilinguistically, to the local language [...] So after a lot of debates people agreed, and I received consent from one of the professors to get his book and make it open and translate into the local language. I told him, 'Making your book open is one good means of promoting your contribution to the world' (Grant Recipient).

Even at this early stage, there is therefore some evidence of impact for the 2025 grants.

The projects we funded in 2024 are at, or near completion. We asked interviewees if they could summarise the impact and importance of OBC funds in a statement. One respondent told us that the Collective Development Fund has been a key driver in increasing the visibility of their institution and institutional press as an open access leader in their country and region:

This grant I had a huge impact on our institution [...] Because now almost every university within the country and in some other universities outside the country and other authors also not from the university, they know now. They now know [our institutional publisher as] the first publisher that is publishing open access electronic books [in the region] (Grant Recipient).

Speaking on the Community Publishing Garden, Kath Burton told us that the funding provided critical time and space to think creatively and collaboratively about publishing, and to convert that contemplation into practice:

[The grant has] enabled two things. One, to think deeply about what we understand and what we feel about community publishing as publishers who publish in community with other publishing types and with a different audience of authors and creators. It's also helped us to put some of that conceptual feeling and thinking into practice. So that personally for me is the biggest bit. If we can overcome some of the challenges of working in imperfect systems, if we can champion the benefits of open publishing within an open book system, then we're going to get greater engagement from both publisher and participant, author or creator. And that for me was something that I hadn't necessarily thought would emerge from this particular project, but it came became the biggest and most unexpected piece of activity and continuity that we might expect to carry on after the end of the project (Kath Burton).

Despite some survey respondents and one interviewee stating that increasing the amount of funding available would be useful, interviewees felt strongly that there is a place for small, agile and flexible grants within the funding landscape, both for emergent and experimental projects and those building on established work:

[smaller sums are] very useful depending on what the organization is planning to do. There are some institutions who have built something already and then that £7,500 will be very useful for them, and they'll be able to pay a lot from it (Grant Recipient).

Both [my project co-lead] and I have been at very nascent stages in building the practices that we have established now. And having seed funding like this just gives us one, some additional validation that we might be doing the right thing and two, a little bit of energy to carry it forward (Kath Burton).

Indeed, this interviewee felt that the more arduous application process and stringent monitoring and reporting required for large grants would not have been accessible to her at the time she started her project, and that future applicants should be assured of the 'scaling small' principles informing the OBC's work:

[A small grant] has a different purpose [to a large one] and it means that different participants can engage. So I wouldn't have been able to engage in any other way at the time. Maybe now it's slightly different, but at the time I wouldn't have been able to engage if this had been a bigger grant. But I was able to engage in this this small way and which has been a huge catalyst for my thinking about what I want to do as a community publisher and [...] if there is anything that you can weave into future iterations of this fund, it would be to encourage participants to keep things small. I think you did that and you talked about scaling small and scaling smaller. We really held on to that (Kath Burton).

5.3.3. Outreach, Communication and Dissemination

In terms of our outreach around the Calls, including associated communications and dissemination, interviewees suggested that we offer the Call in more languages, provide more clarity regarding project scope for the differing levels of funding, and perhaps organise a forum with successful proposals from past calls to demonstrate impact. 2025 awardee Catalina

Torres stressed the importance of identifying and using existing networks (regional, national, publishing-related) and work with non-academic organisations – such as Indigenous, rural, or neighbourhood groups – to reach the most marginalised and remote communities. This aligns with Kath Burton’s point that the OBC funds may be accessible to non-traditional applicants in a way large academic grants are not. Encouragingly, one awardee noted,

In terms of creating awareness about the fund, I believe they've done a brilliant job because I was surprised. I was seeing the Call in some avenues that I didn't expect that they would know about the fund [...] I saw it on AREN [the African Reproducibility Network], I saw it through EIFL [Electronic Information for Libraries], I saw it on the Academy of Sciences in South Africa (Grant Recipient).

Finally, it was suggested that we increase contact and communication between grant recipients, such as via online webinars and conversation hours.

5.4. Reflections and Recommendations

The CDF is clearly succeeding in enabling capacity building, funding projects and infrastructure for OA books in multiple contexts, but in LMICs especially. We are also seeding new networks for collaboration. We consider it a significant achievement for the OBC to become a successful grant-making organization. We have already actioned the suggestion to connect recipients for awardees in our 2025 round, who happened to be located in closer geographic proximity than those in the previous round. We hope this will lead to more regional and national collaboration.

Recipient interviews provide particularly strong evidence of the CDF’s effectiveness in enabling early-stage, capacity-building work, especially in contexts where access to larger or more bureaucratic funding schemes is limited. The interviews reveal how the Fund’s emphasis on bibliodiversity, multilingualism, and infrastructural development resonates with recipients’ institutional missions and local constraints, reinforcing the alignment between programme design and diverse lived realities.

A notable theme is the value placed on process clarity and relational support. Recipients consistently described the application and reporting mechanisms as transparent, proportionate, and encouraging. These features are significant in enabling participation. The optional scope check, in particular, emerges as a key enabler, reducing risk for applicants and lowering the barrier to entry.

While the impacts of 2025-funded projects are necessarily preliminary, interviews already indicate early forms of advocacy, network-building, and institutional visibility that extend beyond immediate project outputs. At the same time, suggestions regarding asynchronous reporting and clearer scoping relative to funding levels point to practical refinements that could further improve accessibility across time zones and institutional capacities.

Taken together, the interview data adds important depth and nuance to the survey findings, particularly by foregrounding the experiences, trade-offs, and contextual constraints that are

less visible in structured responses. Across all interview categories, there is strong convergence around the perceived value of the OBC's collective, values-led approach, coupled with pragmatic recognition of the challenges involved in coordinating diverse stakeholders.

The interviews also highlight the extent to which the OBC operates not only as a funding mechanism, but as an enabling infrastructure and community that supports administrative efficiency, credibility signalling, learning, and experimentation. At the same time, they underscore the ongoing importance of expectation-setting, communication, and transparency as the organisation matures and its scale increases.

Overall, the interview findings strengthen confidence in the OBC's core model, while offering targeted insights into where incremental adjustments – rather than structural change – could further enhance its effectiveness and sustainability.

Improvements that could be actioned, as funding and capacity allow, include:

- More facilitation of recipient networking via virtual communities of practice and introductions.
- Developing a standardised, lightweight reporting templates
- Enabling asynchronous reporting if and when appropriate
- Exploring sustainable increases in funding levels over time
- More multilingual outreach in diverse contexts
- More public examples of outputs from previous rounds, such as books and manuals

6. Collective Development Fund Panellists and Reviewer Feedback

6.1. Collective Development Fund Panellists and Reviewer Survey Responses

We asked our panellists and reviewers how they found the process of participation; what they considered important about the work accomplished by the CDF; and how it could be improved in the coming years both for recipients and reviewers. We did not ask about outreach specifically, as panellists and reviewers are recruited directly from our membership and the broader Copim community.

6.1.1. Processes and Operations

The reviewing and decision-making process was highly commended, which as a new charity, we consider a large success. Reviewers and panellists told us:

The review board was very well prepared in advance, and reviewers/panellists received a lot of support without being coaxed in one direction or another (Anonymous Librarian).

It was a seamless process. I was provided with all of the information required to make the judgment (Anonymous Librarian).

My experience of participating in the review process was excellent. The explanations, support and documentation provided to support the process from beginning to end were very good (OA Expert at Jisc).

I enjoyed the experience of reviewing for the CDF. The amount of time provided for completing the review was sufficiently long, the reviewer questionnaire was helpful for structuring the feedback, and I particularly appreciated the opportunity to join the decision-making panel, which was a valuable opportunity to contextualise the review comments further and in consideration with the other applications - plus it was useful to see how the review feedback was being acted on. I can't think of any ways to improve the process (Representative from University of London Press).

The process was well organised and it was great to read the different applications. It was satisfying to learn about and advocate for the successful projects and their potential impact (Anonymous Service Provider).

Reviewers did note that the work involved a considerable time investment, though the timeline was considered sufficient. One participant also told us that although the process was quite time intensive, they found it a 'valuable professional development exercise' (Thomas Graves, LSE), which is an unpredicted added benefit of the process.

6.1.2. Impact

Our panellists and reviewers considered that the work accomplished by the CDF is vital, particularly regarding the potential impact on global equity. Multiple respondents mentioned this. They told us:

The impact that a CDF grant could make to an institution in the Global South should not be underestimated. It could be completely transformative (Anonymous Librarian).

Primarily, the most important thing is that it supports open access in global south countries where university budgets often cannot stretch to accommodate BPCs (or indeed APCs - though those are beyond the scope of OBC). The focus on building open access books infrastructure in these countries means sustainability is baked into the projects it funds. This will (hopefully) go some way to addressing global inequality in research visibility (Thomas Graves, LSE).

The programme is international, providing support to low and middle-income countries. Much of what we do in the UK is very UK focused and often driven by funder mandates, in particular the REF so it is positive to support and develop projects outside of this (Wendy Taylor, University of Salford).

The fact that the grants are not large is not necessarily a design flaw, as

Providing short term funding to projects designed to increase the quantity, quality, and diversity of open access books. Often projects need a kick start to get going and then use this impetus to develop further/ provide evidence for future funding bids to for longer term sustainability. Given the lack of equity already entrenched in the global publishing ecosystem, the CDF provides tangible opportunities for projects from LMIC countries to explore and develop OA book publishing (OA Expert at Jisc)

The OBC's focus on supporting 'collaboration rather than competition' (OA Expert) was also seen as a strength, 'indicating the willingness to support (and the concrete realization of it) as many partners as possible to create a diverse, inclusive and professional ecosystem for open publishing' (Anonymous Librarian).

6.1.3. Improvements

Reviewers did have some suggestions for improvement, however, noting that a face-to-face conversation might be useful for first-time reviewers 'to alleviate misgivings about being qualified' (OA Expert at Jisc). One participant stated that discussions at the final decision-making panel felt somewhat dominated by stronger voices, though they were ultimately happy with the decisions reached. Another suggested we add guidance for approximately how much reviewers are expected to write for each section (Thomas Graves, LSE).

In terms of how the CDF could further its ambition to build capacity for OA books, suggestions centred on two themes: essentially, more outreach and stakeholder consultation, and more funding. As one put it, 'simply from allocation of more revenue. Because of the financial model, this should hopefully happen organically as the OBC attracts more support' (Representative from White Horse Press). In terms of increasing outreach and peer consultation, there were several suggestions, including consulting directly with presses to meet their needs, or working with 'SciELO, SPARC Africa [or] AJOL [African Journals Online] to discover new networks and reach new audiences' (OA Expert at Jisc). It was also suggested that we share more short-form information such as videos with previous recipients explaining why they applied and how they used their grant (OA expert at Jisc), as an accessible form of outreach to potential applicants. One participant suggested we could engage with research funders 'regarding the way they assess research funding applications [...] funding applications e.g. for postdoctoral fellowships that include a book proposal are often likely to prioritise prestigious publishers rather than diamond open access book publishers' (Thomas Graves at LSE). Two respondents suggested that a 12-month timeframe for projects is quite short, and that some strong applications might

better meet their aims in a longer period. Increasing the timeframe would not necessarily increase the funding required from the OBC, though it would increase the staff time required to administer monitoring and reporting as more projects would be running simultaneously. Finally, it was suggested that as the Fund grows, we might consider 'different categories for applications, e.g. technology, capacity, education/training etc. to ensure diversity in approaches being funded' (Anonymous Service Provider).

6.2. Collective Development Fund Panellists and Reviewer Interview Responses

We interviewed two stakeholders who served as CDF reviewers and panellists: Demmy Verbeke of KU Leuven, who also serves as a library representative on the OBC Board of Stewards, and a representative from Jisc who served as an external OA expert and chose to remain partially anonymous.

6.2.1. Value and Impact of the Collective Development Fund

We first discussed the importance of the Collective Development Fund and its impact. Interviewees were in agreement that the relatively small size and lightweight application process is important in making the grants accessible to a wide range of applicants. Both noted positively that this scale distinguishes the CDF from many funding opportunities:

What definitely helps is that the procedure to apply does not seem to be too complicated in the sense that you have to write page and page and pages of an application, and that it was actually perfectly OK to ask for a moderate sum of money... I think a lot of people if they see OK, I will need to fill in 20 pages and I can only apply if I aim for like 3 million subsidy or something [, then I will not apply]. And of course the way it is marketed: it is, I think, for everybody involved very clear this is meant to help diversity, institutions or initiatives that do not necessarily work in the northern hemisphere. I think that is very clear in in in how it is communicated (Demmy Verbeke, KU Leuven).

There's bigger pots of money that maybe are more easily available for those organisations and projects that are already up and running and know how to access [them], know where to look and how to fill in the forms [...] It takes time to build up the skills of how to fill in funding applications [...] I think it'd be relatively easy for maybe someone who's new to the project funding to complete (Representative from Jisc).

Verbeke thought that for some of our member libraries, those on the more 'radical' or 'trailblazing' end of the spectrum of OA engagement, the CDF may have important symbolic value, distinguishing the OBC as an agent of change in the OA landscape as well as a funding intermediary:

For the trailblazing libraries who have said we want to move some budget into alternatives and towards inclusivity and towards diversity, it is actually very good to be able to see OBC is more than just another way of handling finance (Demmy Verbeke, KU Leuven).

On the other hand, for more conservative institutions, it may be harder to justify the use of funds for projects they have no specific or direct interest in. These institutions, Verbeke believes, are more likely to join the OBC to support particular packages and might be less convinced by the value of the CDF.

6.2.2. Reviewer Experiences

Both interviewees felt that the experience of acting as a panellist and/or reviewer for the CDF was positive and well-organised. Verbeke felt that whilst the workload was significant, the administration, communications and briefings provided made the process manageable: 'because of how well it was prepared, the workload was actually very doable'. The judging panel was commended as having 'a good atmosphere and 'a context that it was conducive for us to give feedback' as opposed to a rushed or overscheduled meeting with 'no room for discussion.' Our other interviewee felt that it might be helpful to provide some more training and induction materials for first-time reviewers, primarily to alleviate 'imposter syndrome':

I've got a librarian's background, but I've definitely felt [...] not having worked in publishing or [...] applying for grants [...] I guess it was a bit of imposter syndrome that maybe I wasn't qualified to make decisions: am I interpreting what they're saying in their in their application correctly? (Representative from Jisc).

It was agreed that it was beneficial for reviewers to attend the final judging panel, if possible, in order to experience the decision-making as an iterative process that is informed by but not dependent on the individual reviews. We also discussed the possibility of creating a peer discussion group for reviewers, with established rules around sharing of material to ensure GDPR compliance, as an additional support mechanism for newcomers.

6.2.3. Improvement to the Call

The OBC has made a concerted effort to increase CDF outreach in 2026, and received a correspondingly higher number of scope checks and applications in a greater diversity of languages than the previous year. In terms of further publicising the CDF, one interviewee elaborated on the idea providing more micro-format information across our social media platforms, such as 'recordings that you can add to social media posts or embed in your website - just really short like 1-2 minutes', or 'graphics with a quote' to 'make the content more a bit more visual', summarising key takeaways from previous projects and providing links to more in-depth blog posts. In our other interview, we discussed the point raised earlier, that for more traditional universities, the appeal and importance of the CDF might not be so clear. Verbeke suggested that to outsiders it might not be clear how the CDF integrates with the OBC's membership model and the rest of its work. He advised that for most libraries, the internal logic would be something like

'We give money to OBC because we would want to support an Open Access book program of that particular publisher' [. The CDF] might be a hard sell to some libraries, not the trailblazing ones, but the more conservatives (Demmy Verbeke, KU Leuven).

The OBC should therefore have a clear internal model of the CDF's rationale and organizational purpose, as well as an outreach and communication plan explaining how the labour, funds, and overheads dedicated to the CDF are both distinct from, but also complement, our broader aims.

6.3. Reflection and Recommendations

We consider the strong endorsement of our reviewing and decision-making procedures to be a significant success to the OBC as a new grant-making organization. The process is perceived as transparent, well organised, and well-supported. We acknowledge that the time commitment is substantial and appreciate our colleagues' understanding of the necessity of diligence in these procedures.

The interviews with reviewers and panellists corroborate survey data indicating strong confidence in the CDF's governance and decision-making processes. Importantly, they illuminate how the lightweight nature of the Fund is not perceived as a weakness, but rather as a deliberate and effective design choice that broadens participation and supports equity-focused objectives.

A key insight from the interviews in particular is the dual function of the CDF: for some library stakeholders, particularly those already committed to experimental or reform-oriented OA practices, the Fund carries symbolic weight as evidence that OBC is an agent of structural change rather than merely a funding intermediary. Conversely, this rationale may be less legible to more conservative institutions, reinforcing the need for clearer articulation of how the CDF integrates with the wider membership model.

The reflections based on reviewers' experiences also highlight an important capacity-building dimension: participation in the review process itself can serve as professional development, though this benefit is unevenly realised and may be accompanied by uncertainty or imposter syndrome for first-time reviewers. This suggests that there may be more opportunities for additional induction or peer support without fundamentally altering the process.

Recommendations for the future that the OBC could action are as follows:

- Provide a guide or short training for new reviewers.
- Offer clearer guidance on expected review length/criteria.
- Consider an expanded timeframe for grants if staff resources allow.

In a large group discussion, there is always a risk of certain voices dominating, but providing further training for participants may increase their confidence in speaking or using the chat function more in a public venue, as well as ensuring chairs are briefed to encourage equitable possibilities of participation from all meeting participants. Of course, the OBC would like to allocate more and/or larger grants should our turnover allow it in future (see Section 7), but we also feel there is benefit in smaller, flexible pots of funding for startup or experimental work. We have already actioned an improved social media outreach campaign for 2026, leveraging our networks beyond the Global North. This has resulted in an increased number of scope checks for this year.

7. Analysis of OBC Finances and Sustainability

7.1. Progress So Far

Since launch, the OBC has made considerable progress. We have succeeded in becoming a registered charity fully embedded in the scholarly system, providing an impactful and vital revenue source for its publishers and service provider members. At the time of writing, we have 98 libraries providing financial support to OBC publisher and publishing service provider members, from libraries in the UK, Europe, USA, Canada, Australia and New Zealand.

These libraries support the ‘Supporter Programmes’ offered by our publisher and service provider members. These are pricing structure for their initiative, with libraries able to support these programmes for 1 or 3 years, with the possibility of this funding being renewed thereafter. These Supporter Programmes into collective ‘Packages’. Packages are the sum total of the costs of all the constituent Supporter Programmes.

We have accrued over £1.7million in funding commitments for these Supporter Programmes to date, with around 89% of our funds going either to our members or to support CDF projects. The remaining roughly 11% is retained by the OBC to support our ongoing operational costs. This portion is charged as ‘fees’ to both our Providers and Libraries.⁷

The OBC has grown its publisher and service provider member base, from 8 at the end of the COPIM project, to 19 at present. We have also allocated £87,000 in Collective Development Fund grants, supporting projects in Argentina, Canada, Columbia, Ethiopia, Nigeria, and Zimbabwe.

7.2. Aiming for Full Sustainability

From the very start of OBC’s work, the aim has been for the organisation to ultimately become fully and independently financially self-sustaining. This aim has perhaps been OBC’s most ambitious. The history of open access and open infrastructure is littered with examples of initiatives that launched with fanfare, for a while attracting interest and sometimes significant levels of funding, but which could not ultimately find a way to sustain themselves independently. There are also more general challenges for initiatives launched over the course of grant funded projects. Too often, initiatives launch and undertake important work for a set period of time – often two or three years – but with this work ceasing when the project ends.

While the OBC will be able to operate independently after the end of the OBF project and is likely to be able to continue to sustain itself at a relatively bare bones level for the foreseeable future (see 7.3), the OBC aims in time to become an organisation that can sustainably operate at full capacity, what we here call ‘full sustainability’. From the 1st May 2026 onwards, the OBC

⁷ These figures represent average fee income. The precise fees that are charged vary according to a number of factors and therefore the average will vary slightly, year on year. Our funding model is described in more detail on our website: https://openbookcollective.org/cms/fixd_page/funding_model/

moves from being more or less fully grant funded, via the Copim OBF project, to being fully reliant on a combination of its reserves and on the new income that we are able to bring in from increased library subscriptions. At present, the OBC is not achieving an operational breakeven. However, we have a clear pathway towards near-full sustainability. This relies on the following assumptions:

- That a combination of reserves built up over the life of the Copim OBF project and projected future income provide the OBC with an operational runway of up to three years, giving the OBC time to move towards eventual operational breakeven.
- That the OBC is able to continue to steadily increase the income it receives from supporting libraries over this period.
- That this income increase is achieved by (a) an increased number of supporting libraries and (b) an increased average subscription amount per supporting library.
- That an important route towards increasing average subscription amounts is libraries, over time, seeing the value of increasing the number of initiatives they support via the OBC.
- That the OBC is able to fulfil its core functions with a staff base of 2 full time and one part time member of staff, supported by a part time contributions in kind by the Managing Director, and maintaining expenditure on core operating overheads.
- That all contributions made by Providers towards the OBC Collective Development Fund (CDF) are treated as wholly separate revenue stream and are not used to fund any non-CDF costs. (The CDF is funded by Providers, who can choose to allocate 5% of the revenue they receive to the Fund. Currently, almost all of our Providers do so).
- That the OBC's work and progress towards sustainability remains overseen by its robust community governance structure, including its elected Board of Stewards, which are the charity's legally designated Trustees, and its Custodians, representing the three OBC member caucuses: Libraries, Publishers, and Service Providers.⁸

These assumptions do not quite get the OBC to 'full sustainability' – this would mean not having to rely on voluntary contributions in kind from a Managing Director. However, they get us close. These assumptions inform a set of projections and scenarios that we have developed, which this section of the report will lay out in detail. We are therefore being as transparent as we can be about the assumptions we are working with, as well as the challenges we will be facing in the coming years. This is in keeping with our values as an organisation. It also shows numerically what we have always known: that the ultimate success or failure of the OBC, and initiatives like it, are a collective responsibility.

⁸ The OBC's governance structure described in full: <https://openbookcollective.org/nav/governance>

7.3. Target Scenario: May 2026 – April 2029

The table below provides an overview of what we, within the OBC, refer to as our ‘Target Scenario’. This is the scenario where all the above assumptions hold true, resulting in operational breakeven at the end of April 2029 (i.e. income fully covers costs, as shown – circled in green – by the absence of an operational loss).

When reading this scenario, it is important to note that the ‘Fee Income’ line represents income *retained* by the OBC, via the fees it collects (on a non-profit basis). These figures do not, therefore, include the full sums of revenue that pass through the OBC (given that, as noted in 7.1, around 89% of this revenue is passed to our publisher and service provider members or used to fund CDF grants). However, these full sums of revenue are shown in a different way in the scenario, in the ‘Average annual subscription per institution’ line. A further nuance should be noted: we expect the additional part time colleague not to join the OBC until later in 2026. This means that ‘Costs’ show as slightly lower in the first six months post-OBF project (May to October, 2026).

Table 7.1: Target scenario, May 2026 – April 2029

Target Scenario (Gradually Increase Average Subscription to 8,000 GBP per Institution by 30 Apr 2029)						
<i>Requires 2.4 Additional Institutions per month (assuming 90% retention, 18% Subscription Growth, No Change to Fee Percentages, 2.5 FTEs)</i>						
	Oct 2026	Apr 2027	Oct 2027	Apr 2028	Oct 2028	Apr 2029
	Projection	Projection	Projection	Projection	Projection	Projection
Number of Supporter Institutions (libraries)	117	131	145	159	173	187
Number of Providers (publishers)	20	21	23	25	27	28
Average annual subscription per institution	5,166	5,638	6,154	6,716	7,330	8,000
<i>Increase since previous period</i>	+9%	+9%	+9%	+9%	+9%	+9%
Fee Income	21,283	34,005	47,972	57,930	68,544	80,616
<i>Increase since previous period</i>	-44%	+60%	+41%	+21%	+18%	+18%
Costs	(56,281)	(70,587)	(76,517)	(77,942)	(79,311)	(80,616)
Profit/(Loss)	(34,999)	(36,582)	(28,546)	(20,013)	(10,766)	-
OBF (Open Book Futures) Grant Income	-	-	-	-	-	-
Collective Development Fund: Contributions from Providers	8,520	13,962	19,936	24,169	28,680	33,813
Collective Development Fund: Grants Paid Out	(21,794)	(16,071)	(19,936)	(24,169)	(28,680)	(33,813)
OBC Development Fund: Net Increase in Reserves	(13,274)	(2,109)	-	-	-	-
Profit/(Loss) including Grants and Donations	(48,273)	(38,691)	(28,546)	(20,013)	(10,766)	-
Reserves						
Collective Development Fund Reserves	52,109	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000
Operational Reserves	197,226	160,644	132,099	112,086	101,319	101,319
Total Funds	249,335	210,644	182,099	162,086	151,319	151,319

This Target Scenario was developed following a collaboration with Research Consulting in early 2025, which helped the OBC develop its sustainability plan. We will now discuss in more detail what this table reveals, as well as the thinking and assumptions that sit behind these figures.

7.3.1. Reserves

During the three years of OBF, as well as the last year of COPIM, the OBC’s operations have been almost wholly supported via grant funding. This means that the OBC has been able to

allocate to its reserves both OBC Supporter Programme fee income and any surplus overhead income received by the OBC, in its role as a consortium partner in the OBF project.

The OBC allocates its reserves to two areas: (a) to Collective Development Fund reserves and (b) to Operational Reserves. This distinction is important: CDF funds cannot be used to cover general operational costs, but only work directly associated with the CDF grant programme, including both the grants themselves and direct CDF-related non-staff costs (e.g. costs for translating the calls and applications, or specific CDF-related promotional activities).

By the end of the OBF project, the OBC is projected to have total reserves of £297,608. This includes projected CDF reserves of £65,383. Post-project, the OBC aims to retain a constant £50,000 CDF reserve, with surpluses being used for grants and other direct CDF costs. This reserve is required to smooth out any CDF cashflow issues.

Operational Reserves are projected to be £232,225. These funds will be crucial for the OBF in the coming years. It provides the OBC a valuable cushion, giving time to continue to increase the income it receives, to reach operational breakeven. Thus, the Target Scenario shows Operational Reserves gradually declining in the three years post-OBF project, to just over £100,000 by the end of the period. The OBC reserves policy requires the charity to retain reserves to cover at least six months of operational costs, to cover major unforeseen events or the costs of operational wind-down, if necessary. Given by the end of April 2029 OBC's costs are projected to be just over £80,000 per six-month period, the Target Scenario is in line with OBC's reserves policy.

7.3.2. Increases in Library Members

Our Target Scenario shows that the OBC needs to consistently deliver an increase in its Supporting Institutions of around 28 institutions per year (a net increase of 2.4 per month), to a total of around 190 by the end of 2029). The OBC is currently supported by close to 100 Library Members.

Achieving this increase will not be easy, and we discuss the risks standing in the way of achieving this objective below (7.3.6). Overall, it will require the OBC to successfully demonstrate to the global library community that it and its publisher and service provider members are providing vitally needed open access publishing services to the scholarly community. We know that achieving these kinds of numbers is, in theory, possible. Table 7.2 shows the total number of institutions (mostly libraries, but some other types of institution) publicly supporting other open publishing initiatives, at the time of writing.

Achieving our target requires work by the OBC Management Team in three interrelated areas. First, and most obviously, it requires outreach to convince institutions (especially libraries and library consortia) that have never supported the OBC to do so for the first time. This outreach can be both direct – establishing contact with particular individuals and groups – and it can be

Table 7.2. Number of institutions supporting other open publishing and open infrastructure initiatives

	Direct-ToOpen	DOAB	DOAJ	Knowledge Unlatched	Open Book Publishers	SCOSS
Number of supporting institutions*	326	310	664	670	274	352

*Not counted in the same way. Figures for Knowledge Unlatched and SCOSS include any institution that has ever supporter/pledged. For the rest, it includes currently supporting institutions. Data collected on 29th March 2026.

indirect – by more general advocacy to the community, in a variety of different ways (e.g. at events, on social media, in webinars, in our materials, etc). During the life of the OBF project, this work has been helped both by the financial resources of the project, for example enabling the OBC team to attend a range of different events, and by the wider support and advocacy of the Copim team. Post-project, this capacity will inevitably be reduced. For example, post-OBF project we have an annual budget of approximately £5,000 per year for travel and events – this will allow members of the OBC to attend some key conferences, but these will have to be chosen carefully.

Second, it requires work to retain the support of institutions. OBC subscriptions are typically for a one or a three-year term. As this term comes to an end, the renewal of this subscription is not certain. Perhaps the previous support came from funds that are no longer available at the point of renewal. Perhaps the library has other priorities, or is dissatisfied in some way with the OBC’s work and services. A lot of work within the OBC goes into managing this process. We ensure that we are engaging in diverse ways with our existing library supporters, both individually but also collectively, both at events and at our periodic publisher-library forums. And recently, we have implemented a new workflow that combines information from our accounts team with a dedicated Customer Relationship Management (CRM) service, to ensure that we are engaging libraries in a timely manner, with accurate information about their subscription. The Target Scenario is currently based on a target renewal rate of 90%. The average renewal rate for the past three years has actually been higher than this, at 97%. As such, the Target Scenario currently takes a conservative view on subscription renewals.

Third, it requires work to increase the geographic diversity of our supporting libraries. Currently, the OBC is supported by universities from 12 different countries.⁹ By far the largest number of supporters are from the UK and the USA. This is likely because of (a) OBC’s roots in the first Copim project, which focused its work primarily on these two countries, (b) the fact that it is in these two countries where the OBC and Copim teams have the greatest pre-existing networks, and (c) the skew, amongst OBC’s publisher and service provider members, to initiatives either

⁹ Currently: Australia, Canada, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, USA. A recent breakdown is provided in our most recent Annual Report: <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/open-book-collective-2024-to-2025-annual-report/>

based in the UK or the US, or operating predominantly in English. We have been working to increase the diversity of our library supporters on several fronts. This includes campaigns of direct engagement with libraries and consortia in Continental Europe in particular, as well as seeking to increase the diversity of our publishers, especially. We will discuss to the latter in the next section.

7.3.3. Increases in Provider Members

Our Target Scenario includes an expected increase in the number of Providers – i.e. our publisher and service provider members – from the current 19, to 28 by the end of April 2029 (a close to 50% increase). As noted in the previous section, we see increasing the number and particularly the geographic diversity of our publisher members as connected to our ability to increase our number of library supporters. It is also potentially important in increasing the average subscription amount, as we will discuss in the next section.

This aim is perhaps the most readily achievable of our targets. Since the start of the OBF project, we have seen a steady stream of applications for membership. The result has been a more than doubling of Provider members of the OBC, increasing from 8 to 19 over the period. This has enabled us to increase the diversity of the type of initiatives available to support via the OBC (including in 2024 announcing our first university press members¹⁰), their geography (including new initiatives based in Belgium, Canada, Italy, and Germany), and the language of their output (including two German-language publishers, another publishing numerous Italian works, and yet another publishing some Dutch texts).¹¹

The steady stream of applications continues. At present, we have no plans to impose a cap on the number of publishers and service providers that can join the OBC (if they meet our membership criteria), however this is something that we are constantly keeping under review.

7.3.4. Increases in Average Subscription Amount

The Target Scenario includes a potential increase in the subscription amounts from institutions, up to a target average subscription of £8,000 per institution by the end of April 2029. As a reminder, the OBC's model operates as follows: the OBC agrees, with each publisher and service provider members, a tiered 'Supporter Programme' pricing structure for their initiative, which are then grouped into collective 'Packages' available to subscribe to, by libraries. These Packages are the sum total of the costs of all the constituent Supporter Programmes.

¹⁰ Open Book Collective (2024), Three University Presses join the Open Book Collective.

<https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/three-new-university-presses-join-the-open-book-collective/>

¹¹ The new initiatives are: Edizioni Ca' Foscari (based in Italy, languages include English and Italian); Leuven University Press (based in Belgium, languages include Dutch and English); PKP, based in Canada; Verfassungsblog (based in Germany, publishing mainly in German); Verlag Barbara Budrich (based in Germany, languages include English and German).

The largest Package is the 'Open Book Collective Package'. For this Package, the supporting institution subscribes to the Supporter Programmes from all our Provider Members. As noted, the OBC currently offers Supporter Programmes from 19 Members. Depending on the Tier an institution falls into, this translates into a cost ranging from £7,910 To £26,100 per year.

If all our current Library Members supported this complete Package, then the OBC would easily reach its average £8,000 per year target. But of course, for various reasons, institutions do not and, often, cannot. Why, then, does the model include a projected increase in this average subscription amount?

The first reason is that we have already seen that, so far, there has been a direct relationship between the growth of the OBC and average subscription amounts from libraries. In the three years of the OBF project, the average subscription amount has increased by 56% (from £3,160 to £4,924). In the next three years, it is at least conceivable that the OBC could achieve similar growth (the target is a 55% increase).

There are likely two primary factors that have driven average subscription growth to date. One is the growth in size of the OBC (see 7.3.3.): making more publishers and service providers available to support via the OBC provides universities with a greater range of options to support, with the average subscription cost increasing particularly when an institution decides it can support the complete OBC package.

The other is likely associated with the growth of OBC's reputation in the sector. The OBC is still a new, and for many still unknown organisation. However, to those that we have been engaging with, we hope to have demonstrated that we are an organisation that can be trusted with the support we gratefully receive. This includes ensuring that this support goes to publishers producing peer-reviewed work of the highest quality, that are deeply committed to open access, being supported by publishing service providers developing much needed, robust open infrastructures, all assessed via stringent membership criteria. It is likely that there is some relationship between the degree to which libraries or consortia are willing to support the OBC and the degree to which they see the above as being evidenced, over time. We believe that as the OBC further consolidates its work as a still resolutely community-governed and non-profit organisation, this trust will further increase.

There is a third potential factor which we have seen some evidence of and which could ultimately play a determining role in whether initiatives like the OBC have a long-term future in the sector. At the start of OBC's life, the funding we received was often from library underspend at the end of a financial period, or some similar ad hoc budget line. However, over the life of the OBF project, at least in some local and national contexts, we have seen increasing efforts by libraries and funders to work to support Diamond open access initiatives in more systematic ways. Sometimes, this takes the form of guidance to libraries by particular groups or

consortia.¹² Some libraries are also creating dedicated Diamond open access budgets for the first time (including via divestments from commercial publishing subscriptions).¹³ And some funders have made explicit that libraries are permitted to use the funding they receive to fund Diamond open access and scholarly communications initiatives.¹⁴ We see hopeful signs in each of these areas, with the obvious caveat that for supporting Diamond open access to become not an exception but the norm, this work has to scale, significantly.

7.3.5. Collective Development Fund

Our Target Scenario also includes projections relating to our CDF grant giving programme. As noted earlier (7.3.1.), over the life of the OBF project, we have been able to accrue not only operational reserves, but also reserves for the CDF.

Table 7.1. shows that, if the OBC meets its income targets, we will be able to gradually increase our average annual CDF-related payments from just over £40,000 in the May 2026 to April 2027 period, to just over £60,000 in the May 2028 to April 2029 period, while consistently retaining the £50,000 CDF reserve. This programme is important to us: it means that we are working not only to support our publisher and service provider members, but also the wider ecosystem, in the process enhancing the bibliodiversity of the open book publishing landscape. Increasing the amount awarded within the next three years by around 50% would only strengthen that work.

7.3.6. Risks and Mitigations

So far, we have only discussed our Target Scenario. We appreciate that meeting the targets we have outlined will be a challenge, especially in the context of an increasingly fragile global economy and fragile higher education sector. However, we hope that the above has shown at least a path to meeting our aim of becoming fully financially self-sustaining.

We certainly acknowledge that there a number of risks that threaten our ability to meet our targets during the period. Table 7.3. highlights some of these risks, as well as mitigations that we have put in place.

¹² See for example RLUK (2026), Shared Principles for the Evaluation and Acquisition of Open Access Monograph Model. <https://www.rluk.ac.uk/shared-principles-open-access-monograph-models/>

¹³ Noteworthy examples are the various Diamond/Open Scholarly Communications Funds created by a group of Universities in the Netherlands, including at Delft University of Technology, Erasmus University Rotterdam, the University of Amsterdam, and Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. These innovations were recently discussed at the most recent UKSG conference: Otting-Geevers, L., P. Braak, A. van den Maagdenberg, E. C. Yu, and P. Sijrier-Goettsch (2026), Diamond Open Scholarly Communication Fund Panel, *UKSG 49th Annual Conference*. <https://www.uksg.org/events/conference26/#programme>.

¹⁴ For example, Wellcome allowing its block grant to be used to support scholarly communications infrastructures: <https://wellcome.org/research-funding/guidance/open-access-guidance/open-access-funding> or UKRI enabling some funding for Diamond open access initiatives, via their Open Access Fund for Long Form Publications: <https://www.ukri.org/publications/guidance-for-ukris-open-access-fund-for-long-form-publications/>

Table 7.3. Risks and mitigations for the Open Book Collective

Risk	Likelihood	Impact	Risk ranking	Mitigation
Higher education funding crisis continues to deepen, impacting library budgets	High	High	Very High	Working collaboratively with other initiatives to consistently argue that in a context of financial constraint Diamond OA is a solution, not a problem. Encouraging libraries to learn from other libraries that are already reallocating portions of funding saved from cancelling commercial subscriptions to Diamond OA initiatives, including by hosting webinars and other outreach events highlighting library best practices.
An inability of OBC's slimmed down team and budgets to deliver the outreach goals and service expectations of library and service provider members and/or in-kind, voluntary contributions from the OBC Managing Director are insufficient to meet OBC's operational requirements.	Medium	High	High	Furthering already in progress work to develop supplementary income streams. One option being considered is adding the option for universities to be able to support the OBC directly. This could help us exceed targets and increase our staffing and outreach budgets beyond the current bare minimum, potentially to also include a salaried Managing Director. In addition, completing ongoing work to develop a set of indicators which will help more clearly and transparently communicate our progress against our financial goals to members. To include more detailed information on potential 'trigger points' which require the OBC to either adjust its model or make savings. Finally, launching a new Transition Support Working Group, including publisher and service provider members, to deliver additional support to the OBC as it matures.
The OBC's offer being crowded out by other new, Diamond OA and open infrastructure initiatives.	Medium	High	High	Intensifying our already active advocacy on the importance of collaboration across Diamond OA and open infrastructure initiatives in this space. Deepening our collaboration with other initiatives – notably Open Journals Collective (OJC), with whom we have recently signed a Memorandum of Understanding, and Thoth Open Metadata – to develop new shared infrastructures and workflows, to enhance our reporting and outreach capacities, and to increase operational efficiencies.
Libraries and consortia shift support away from Diamond OA towards other funding models (e.g. alternative versions of OA, or new closed access models), potentially leading to knock on impacts for the OBC (e.g. falling subscriptions undermining trust in the organisation)	Medium	Medium	Moderate	Focusing outreach efforts directly on the library and consortia communities, including via our regular library forums, and via webinars and other events organised in collaboration with others.
National-level policies shift focus away from Diamond-OA, for example to Green or Gold OA models, or deprioritise support for OA in general, perhaps as other issues occupy their attention (e.g. AI, research security, digital sovereignty).	Medium	Medium	Moderate	Deepening our ongoing work with wider communities to influence policy. For example, the OBC, via its work with OPERAS, is an active participant in the Policy Forum that has been set up as an output of the PALOMERA project. ¹⁵ The OBC team is also engaging policy makers in a UK context, in collaboration with other colleagues, including in the Copim community and involved in the Open Institutional Publishing Association (OIPA).
The OBC failing in its aim to successfully appeal beyond the anglosphere, reducing the pool of libraries open to supporting its work.	Low	High	Moderate	Further extending our current focus on engaging colleagues across Continental Europe in particular, including presenting at relevant local events and further expanding the range of languages our website can be shown in (currently, it is available in English and German). In addition, working to recruit further non-Anglophone publishers as members of the OBC.

¹⁵ Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area, funded by the European Union from 2023 to 2024: <https://operas-eu.org/projects/past-projects/palomera/>

7.4. Fallback and Emergency Scenarios

In addition, alongside our Target Scenario, we also have a Fallback Scenario and an Emergency Scenario. If the OBC proves unable to get sufficiently close to the previously outlined financial targets, we can move to alternate models.

The Fallback Scenario involves reducing our staffing from 2.5 Full Time Equivalent (FTE) to 1.5FTE, potentially supported by volunteer ambassadors, a level that would enable the OBC to maintain its existing subscriptions base for a limited time period, while likely losing the prospect of any significant increases, given that library and publisher outreach would be of any significant increases, given that library and publisher outreach would be significantly scaled back. The work of the Collective Development would also have to be paused during this period, due to a lack of staff capacity, with the primary focus on effective subscriptions management, and some limited outreach, supported in part by ambassadors. The Fallback Scenario is not a realistic long-term model for the OBC. However, it would give the OBC time to obtain an alternate income stream (e.g. grant funding), or to revise its financial model.

There is also an Emergency Scenario, in which staffing is reducing to 1.0FTE. In this Scenario, the focus is purely on effective subscriptions management, with little to no outreach. As the title suggests, the Emergency Scenario is primarily designed to extend the period of organisational survival, even if at the cost of gradually falling subscriptions (a trend at risk of being exacerbated by falling trust in the organisation amongst stakeholders). Again, however, this Scenario would at least provide the OBC with time to change course.

Based on the latest projections for total OBC revenue received by the end of the OBF project, reaching the Fallback Scenario, with 1.5FTE staffing, requires the OBC to meet a target income of £104,450 per year, an increase of 106% on latest projections for income £50,802 for the final twelve months of the OBF project. This compares to the Target Scenario, which requires a target income of £161,222 per year, an increase of 217% on projected income for the final year of the OBF project. Reaching the Emergency Scenario, with 1.0FTE staffing, requires a target income of £76,182 per year, an increase of 50% on projected income for the final year of the OBF project.¹⁶

As discussed in the previous section (7.3.6.), we are in the process of developing a set of indicators that will help make clear if and when the OBC should start seriously planning for the Fallback or Emergency Scenarios. These will be for use both internally, by the OBC Management Team, and in the OBC Management Team's discussions with publisher, service provider, and library members.

Of course, neither the Fallback nor the Emergency Scenario reflect our expectations for the OBC's progress in the next three years. Switching to these Scenarios as anything other than an

¹⁶ These figures are based on ongoing, in progress work by our accounts support team to develop a new set of indicators for use by the OBC. As such, they should be treated as provisional and could potentially be subject to future revisions.

interim measure would likely eventually mean falling support for our publishers, our service providers, and for the wider ecosystem served by the Collective Development Fund. This would likely significantly inhibit the expansion of longform Diamond open access publishing across the sector, at least as led by the OBC. However, by laying out these possibilities, we hope to both demonstrate our commitment to transparency in open infrastructure development, and to make clear what is at stake, in the collective and collaborative funding of Diamond open access book publishing. We need all the support – both financial and in kind – that those communities invested in similar ambitions to ours are able to offer.

8. Concluding Reflections and Summary of Recommendations

8.1. Concluding Reflections

This evaluation demonstrates that the OBC has, since its launch, largely succeeded in establishing itself as a trusted intermediary and enabling body in the open access books landscape. Across all the respondent groups – libraries, publishers and service providers, Collective Development Fund recipients, and reviewers – there is a consistent endorsement of the OBC’s mission, values, and principles. In particular, respondents emphasised the importance of collaboration over competition, support for Diamond OA over BPCs, and the role of the OBC in enabling bibliodiversity. Respondents also outlined a range of significant impacts that the OBC is delivering. For publishers, OBC income is succeeding in helping them publish more OA books, with better metadata, that are disseminated more widely than would otherwise be the case. For service providers, OBC income is helping them enhance their services and is providing them with significant assistance on their own paths towards full financial sustainability. For Collective Development Fund recipients, OBC funding is kick starting new important new areas of work on open access book publishing, often by galvanising enthusiasm and energy in specific national and regional contexts.

One key lesson from our stakeholder consultations is that mission alignment is a primary driver of engagement. Library, publisher, and service provider members are often motivated less by short-term specific returns than by participation in a collective effort to reshape scholarly publishing infrastructures in more equitable and sustainable ways. This suggests that the OBC’s value proposition meets ethical and strategic concerns of the communities it serves. This is an important finding. However, the evaluation also highlights that values alignment does not remove the need for practical tools, particularly for internal advocacy and financial justification.

A second key lesson concerns the diverse but complementary forms of value experienced by those that respectively provide and receive financial support via the OBC. Financial support – whether through the supporter programme or the Collective Development Fund – is impactful, particularly in enabling flexible, non-BPC-based publishing and capacity building in diverse contexts. However, respondents consistently pointed to non-monetary benefits as equally important: reduced administrative burden, reputational signalling, knowledge exchange, professional development, and participation in a community of practice. Recognising and highlighting this broader value proposition will be important for future OBC communications and outreach.

The evaluation highlights a productive tension between flexibility and predictability. The OBC’s model does not guarantee income or outcomes for its publisher and service provider

members. While this is well understood by many participants, some publisher and service provider members expressed uncertainty around timelines, potential income levels, and renewal processes. A key lesson here is the importance of expectation-setting and clear communication, not to undermine the collective model, but to ensure that participants can plan realistically within it.

In relation to the Collective Development Fund, the findings indicate that small, targeted grants can indeed have significant impact, particularly when combined with transparent processes, supportive review structures, and a focus on capacity rather than outputs alone. The emphasis on LMIC contexts and infrastructure development is seen as both ethically important and effective. However, the evaluation also points to opportunities to strengthen peer connection between recipients, reduce administrative friction where possible, and make funded outputs more visible and accessible as examples and inspiration for future applicants.

The evaluation also underscores that the OBC is successfully operating not only as a funding mechanism, but as a community. This has always been our intention. The OBC's role in convening stakeholders, facilitating knowledge exchange, and supporting advocacy within institutions is already evident, and could be further developed. There is strong appetite amongst participants to consolidate and advance the community-based benefits of the model.

Finally, our analysis of OBC's financial sustainability plans shows a viable path towards financial sustainability, developed according to realistic assumptions and expectations about the appetite for collective, Diamond open access funding models like ours and how this translates into the support we receive. We also hope to have shown that we are engaging seriously with the risks that stand in the way of achieving these goals and are mitigating these as best we can.

Overall, we hope that readers agree that this evaluation has shown that the OBC is largely working as intended, with continued and expanding support, can in time become fully embedded as a permanent fixture in the open publishing ecosystem. The lessons emerging from this evaluation are less about any fundamental change than about consolidation: improving communication, strengthening onboarding and advocacy support, deepening international engagement, and continuing to invest in the communal and infrastructural work that underpins collective approaches to open access book publishing.

8.2. Summary of Recommendations

While the evaluation findings are largely positive, they do point to several areas where the OBC can strengthen its operations, communication, and processes as it matures.

A recurring theme across the data is the need for **clearer and more consistent communication**, particularly for new or prospective participants. While some publisher and service provider members have a strong understanding of the OBC's collective model, others

expressed uncertainty around practical aspects such as anticipated income, renewal processes, timelines, and so on. Improving **onboarding materials, FAQs, and expectation-setting communications** would help ensure that participants are able to engage confidently and advocate for more involvement within their own institutions.

Relatedly, the evaluation highlights an opportunity to strengthen how the OBC supports current or potential library members to develop **internal justifications for supporting, or continuing to support, the OBC**. Although values alignment is high, respondents noted that securing and maintaining institutional support requires clear narratives, metrics, or examples that can be shared with budget holders. Developing **advocacy toolkits including case studies, summary impact statements, or adaptable briefing materials** could significantly reduce the burden on individual librarians while reinforcing the collective nature of the programme.

The findings also suggest potential to improve **visibility and feedback loops**, particularly regarding the Collective Development Fund. While recipients report that funding has had important impact, awareness of funded projects among the wider community is uneven. More **systematic sharing of funded activities**, lessons learned, and longer-term outcomes in **shorter and accessible formats** would help demonstrate impact, support knowledge exchange, and provide clearer indicators to potential applicants about the types of work the Fund supports.

Another area for development concerns **community and peer exchange**. Respondents value the sense of community fostered by the OBC, but there is appetite for **more structured and real-time interactions**, particularly between publishers, service providers, and CDF recipients. While capacity constraints must be considered, even modest facilitation of peer learning (for example, **themed discussions, showcases, or webinars**) could deepen the OBC's role as a community of practice.

The analysis of OBC finances and post-OBF sustainability show **the need to increase mitigations** against a number of identified risks, in order to be able to at least meet the progress mapped out in our Target Scenario. Particularly high priority mitigations include working collaboratively with other colleagues and initiatives to **consistently argue that in a context of financial constraint Diamond OA is a solution, not a problem, deepening our collaboration with other initiatives** – notably Open Journals Collective and Thoth Open Metadata, **furthering work to develop supplementary income streams, over and above fee income**, as well as **completing ongoing work to develop a more granular set of indicators** against which to assess OBC's ongoing financial progress.

Overall, these areas for improvement do not indicate weaknesses in the OBC's core model and ways of working. Rather, they reflect the challenges of transitioning from an early-stage initiative to a more established intervention in the field of scholarly publishing. Addressing them will help consolidate existing strengths while enabling the OBC to support a broader and more diverse set of participants in the years ahead.

Appendix 1: Acknowledgements from the Managing Director

I would like to thank the two funders of the COPIM and OBF projects – Arcadia and Research England. Particular thanks to Ross Mounce at Arcadia, and Steven Hill and Peter Seddon at Research England. My deep thanks to those stakeholders who contributed to this evaluation, as well as to all our library supporters and publisher and service provider members. And I would like to offer my sincere appreciation to all those who have played pivotal roles in the development of the OBC, including all our past and present board members, of whom I would like to particularly thank Eileen Joy (punctum books), who co-led the development of the OBC during the COPIM project, Rupert Gatti (Open Book Publishers, Open Journals Collective & Thoth Open Metadata), who continues to play a key role in shaping the OBC’s business model and strategy, and Lidia Uziel (UC Santa Barbara) and Niels Stern (OAPEN/DOAB), who have led the OBC board as Chair and Vice-Chair respectively, performing a number of vital roles within the organisation as part of this. Thanks to Janneke Adema and Judith Fathallah, who, with Eileen, developed the OBC’s governance structure, and thanks again to Judith for leading the stakeholder evaluation research. I am hugely grateful to those that have worked or are working directly for and with the OBC. Over the course of the OBF project, this includes Caroline Ball, Francesca Corazza, Arturo Garduño-Magaña, Judith Fathallah, Izabella Penier, Kevin Sanders and Livy Onalee Snyder, all of whom have made significant contributions to helping consolidate the OBC as an organisation. Thanks also to Elli Gerakopoulou and Dan Rudmann, for their early contributions to helping conceptualise the OBC. Our partnership with Thoth Open Metadata has been vital throughout, so thanks to all the Thoth team, and especially Toby Steiner, Javier Arias, and Hannah Hillen. Thanks to colleagues at Lancaster University who have supported our work, and especially Andrew Barker, Joanne Fitzpatrick, Claire McGann, Tom Morley, Sue Pell, and Elaine Sykes. I would also like to thank the wider OBF and COPIM teams for all the support they have provided to the OBC, which far exceeded what could have been reasonably expected. Thanks to Martin Eve and Andy Byers for their considerable work on developing the OBC’s online platform, to Rob Johnson, Katie Fraser, and Katharine Szamuely at Research Consulting for their help in refining our strategy and post-project financial sustainability model, as well as to Chris and Natasha at NTN Limited for their ongoing accountancy and projections modelling support. Others I would like to thank for various forms of collaboration with the OBC over the course of OBF include Reggie Raju and Jill Claasen at University of Cape Town Libraries, Omo Oaiya at WACREN, Caroline Edwards at Open Journals Collective, Open Library of Humanities and Birkbeck, University of London, Tom Shaw at Open Journals Collective, Pierre Mounier and the wider OPERAS community, the Open Institutional Publisher’s Association (especially Paula Kennedy at University of London Press and Phillipa Grand at LSE Press), Vanessa Proudman at SPARC Europe, including for detailed comments on a draft of this report, Sharla Lair at Lyrasis, and Kaitlin Thaney, Katherine Skinner and Emmy Tsang at Invest in Open Infrastructures. *Joe Deville, April 2026*

Appendix 2: Survey Questions

A2.1. For Member Libraries

How did you/your institution hear about the work of the OBC?

Why did you/your institution decide to join and support the OBC?

Which aspects of the OBC's work do you consider the most important? Why are these important?

Have there been any direct benefits of supporting the OBC for you/your institution? If so, what have these benefits been?

How could the OBC improve the ways it serves and works with its library members?

How could the OBC improve the ways it conducts outreach to potential supporters?

Do you have any other comments or feedback you would like to share?

- How would you prefer for your feedback to be used in any resulting outputs
- Fully anonymous (e.g. attributed only to 'a librarian')
- Partially anonymous (e.g. 'Representative from Example Library')

Not anonymous (name and organization acknowledged -- e.g. 'Sarah Jones, from Example Library')

Would you be interested in taking part in a followup interview of up to 1 hour, hosted on Microsoft Teams?

- Yes
- No

A2.2. For Publishers and Publishing Service Providers

Why did you decide to join the OBC?

What was your experience of the application and onboarding process? Are there any ways it could be improved?

What benefits has being an OBC member brought you?

Is there one particular positive impact or success story that has resulted from OBC funding? If so, could you provide some detail?

How could the OBC improve the ways it serves and works with its publisher/service provider members?

Do you have any suggestions for how the OBC could enhance the way it engages with potential library supporters?

Do you have any other comments or feedback you would like to share?

How would you prefer for your feedback to be used in any resulting outputs?

- Fully anonymous (e.g. attributed only to 'a publisher/service provider')
- Partially anonymous (e.g. 'Representative from Example Publisher')
- Not anonymous (name and organization acknowledged -- e.g. 'Sarah Jones, from Example Service Provider')

Would you be interested in taking part in a followup interview of up to 1 hour, hosted on Microsoft Teams?

- Yes
- No

A2.3. For Collective Development Fund Awardees

How did you hear about the CDF?

What was your experience with the application process? Are there any ways it could be improved?

Is there one particular positive impact or success story that has resulted from CDF funding? If so, could you provide some detail?

How could the OBC spread awareness of the CDF programme, to increase the number of applications in future?

How have you found the reporting requirements? How could they be improved?

Are there any other ways we improve the CDF either for successful projects or for applicants?

Do you have any other comments or feedback you would like to share?

Would you be interested in taking part in a followup interview of up to 1 hour, hosted on Microsoft Teams?

- Yes
- No

A2.4. For Collective Development Fund Panellists and Reviewers

What do you consider to be important about the CDF grant programme?

How was your experience in acting as a reviewer/panellist? Are there any ways it could be improved?

Do you have suggestions for how the CDF could further meet its goals in building capacity for OA books?

Do you have any other comments or feedback you would like to share?

How would you prefer for your feedback to be used in any resulting outputs?

- Fully anonymous (e.g. attributed only to 'a publisher/service provider')
- Partially anonymous (e.g. 'Representative from Example Publisher')
- Not anonymous (name and organization acknowledged -- e.g. 'Sarah Jones, from Example Service Provider')

Would you be interested in taking part in a followup interview of up to 1 hour, hosted on Microsoft Teams?

- Yes
- No

Appendix 3: Projects So Far Funded by the Collective Development Fund

A3.1. First Call: 2024

A3.1.1. Fostering Academic Self-Reliance in Nigeria through Open Access Books

- Host organisation: [Federal University of Technology Minna](#) (FUTMinna)
- Led by: Prof. Abdulsalami Kovo, FUTMinna, Nigeria (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1356-2948>)
- Country: Nigeria
- Award: £15,000

Building on recent OA book advocacy in Nigeria, [the Academic Publishing Centre \(APC\)](#) at the Federal University of Technology Minna (FUTMinna) undertook this project to meet the critical demand for locally authored academic materials within Nigerian universities. Utilizing [Datasphir](#), a local open-source digital infrastructure provider, a sustainable platform has been established to empower Nigerian scholars and educators to create, produce, and disseminate high-quality open access books. This has been accomplished via a series of collaborative writing workshops hosted nationwide in collaboration with other Academic Publishing Centres in Nigeria's six geopolitical zones. These specialised workshops, guided by experienced facilitators, empowered authors and librarians to engage in intensive content creation, honing their skills in book production. This project answers a critical need for locally authored, openly accessible educational materials in Nigeria. Beyond serving as a pilot, it will act as a demonstrator for similar initiatives in the region. [See the latest update here.](#)

A3.1.2. Enhancing Open Access Book Publishing at Chinhoyi University of Technology (CUT) Library

- Host organisation: Chinhoyi University of Technology (CUT)
- Led by: Dr. Josiline Chigwada, University of South Africa, South Africa (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0964-3582>)
- Country: Zimbabwe
- Award: £15,000

Utilizing [Open Monograph Press](#) (OMP), this project has established a sustainable infrastructure for open access book publishing at CUT, provided capacity-building workshops for the authors and editors on open access publishing practices, and is now working to publish a series of high-quality open access books across diverse disciplines, and develop

promotional strategies to increase the visibility and impact of open access publishing in Zimbabwe. Project activities included building the website for the open access book publishing initiative; training of the CUT Library scholarly team in the use of OMP at the [University of Cape Town](#); training of peer reviewers on the use of OMP; and solicitation and review of book proposals. [See the latest update here.](#)

A3.1.3. The Community Publishing Garden: Centring Grassroots Publishing Initiatives in the Open Book Publishing System

- Host organisation: [Radish Press](#)
- Led by: Zoe Wake Hyde, Radish Press, Canada (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9523-6635>) and Kath Burton, Publicly Engaged Publishing, UK (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7785-9604>)
- Countries: Canada and UK
- Award: £7,500

This project has launched a model of participatory exchange for publishing practitioners and community members to better serve the forms of knowledge emerging from grassroots communities (projects and programmes that are defined by the wants and needs of the people involved). Taking inspiration from permaculture principles (earth care, people care, fair share), The Community Publishing Garden centres and supports grassroots publishing initiatives in the open book publishing system, comprising a digital space for community engagement, collaboration and design. The aim is to develop radically inclusive open publishing models that support the diverse forms of knowledge production emerging from grassroots communities. [See the latest update here.](#)

A3.2. Second Call: 2025

A3.2.1. Empowering Ethiopian Research Universities: A Multifaceted Approach to Overcome Open Access Barriers in Scholarly Publishing

- Host Organization: [Haramaya University](#)
- Led by: Professor Tilahun Shiferaw (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1335-5575>)
- Country: Ethiopia
- Award: £7,500

This project tackles systemic barriers hindering open access (OA) scholarly publishing in Ethiopia, including cultural resistance, language disparities and infrastructure and policy gaps. By engaging academic communities via workshops and advocacy, it aims to shift perceptions toward OA adoption. In collaboration with [Electronic Information for Libraries](#) (EIFL), key interventions will include developing policies to translate contents to local-languages to bridge

linguistic divides, establishing open access institutional repository at Haramaya University, and drafting national OA policy guidelines to institutionalise best practices.

A3.2.2. Knowledge Accessible to the Community: CLACSO as a Platform to Democratize Scholarly Publishing in Latin America and the Caribbean

- Host Organization: [CLACSO](#)
- Led by: María Fernanda Pampín and Pablo Vommaro (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6957-0453>)
- Country: Argentina
- Award: £12,000

Building on CLACSO's history of researching, implementing, and disseminating Diamond open access, this project addresses asymmetry between associated centers in Latin America regarding knowledge of open access (OA) both from a conceptual perspective and its technical implementation. This project will create structured training opportunities to provide essential conceptual and technical tools for Diamond open access and its implementation, and build infrastructure to allow knowledge dissemination through an easily accessible and sustainable virtual platform.

A3.2.3. Capacity Building Strategy for Access and Publication of Open Access Academic Books for Small and Medium-Sized Higher Education Institutions in Southwestern Colombia

- Host Organization: [Fundación Universitaria Católica Lumen Gentium](#)
- Led By: Catalina del Mar Garrido Torres (<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-6089-858X>) and Wilson Martinez Guaca (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6059-9383>)
- Country: Colombia
- Award: £15,000

This project will strengthen capacity for and access to and publishing high-quality academic open access (OA) books produced by researchers at several institutions across Colombia. The strategy involves supporting the development of infrastructure within these institutions – not only for publishing their specific outputs, but also for establishing a training program that builds capacity for publishing open access (OA) books. A shared portal will be created to disseminate these publications, prioritizing editorial lines that promote bibliodiversity and align with the educational and research innovations of these institutions – such as intercultural dialogue, environmental and sustainable development, and studies on peace and post-conflict. The project will also deliver a handbook of practical guidelines arising from the training process.

A3.2.4. Enhancing Library Publishing Service through OA Book Publishing at Addis Ababa University Library

- Led By: Getnet Lemma Tefera
- Country: Ethiopia
- Award: £15,000

By utilizing the PKP Open Monograph Press (OMP), this initiative will create a sustainable framework for open access book publishing within the Addis Ababa University library. It will also offer capacity-building workshops for authors and editors on open access book publishing practices and will produce a series of high-quality open access academic textbooks across various disciplines. This project responds to a current lack of local academic materials, as scholars are often dissuaded from disseminating their knowledge through publications due to the high expenses involved in publishing. It will facilitate collaboration and resource sharing through a networked community among the academic institutions all over the country through an established institution of library consortia Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL), developing working open access book publishing model for the academic community and publication platform freely available to all scholars. Through the various capacity building workshops for authors, editors and curators the project aims to develop a community of open access book publishing and contribute to global academic knowledge exchange.